

Accepted Author Manuscript

Journal: Water, Air & Soil pollution

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This is the peer-reviewed accepted manuscript. The final version is available at:
[<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-024-07033-4>]

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Microplastics pollution in shellfish aquaculture: Occurrence, impact, and possible remedies

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Abstract

Microplastics (MPs) contamination, which originated from anthropogenic activities, is one of the environmental challenges posing a threat to aquaculture systems globally. Occurrence of MPs pollution has been found to affect the commercially important farmed shellfish organisms in many recent studies. Considering the interconnected repercussions, this paper reviews and assesses the likely sources of microplastics in shellfish farming, as well as their behavioral, physical, and genetic effects on shellfish products. Microplastics penetration and deposition by various shellfish may result in unique health and performance deterioration, such as toxicological implications, behavioral changes, growth and reproductive issues. These negative consequences are leading the shellfish aquaculture industry to an unsustainable future. Finally, potential solutions are presented to mitigate the negative effects of microplastic pollution in shellfish cultures, such as controlling microplastics through water treatment technology, limiting plastic usage in aquaculture, ecological concepts, the use of alternative plastic products, and policy implications.

Keywords: food safety, health risks, microplastic contamination, policy, shellfish aquaculture, treatment technology

1. Introduction

Over the past few decades, microplastics pollution has emerged as a global environmental challenge that affects marine ecosystems and potentially the human health. Microplastics (MPs), defined as plastic particles smaller than 5 millimeters, are ubiquitous in the oceans and can accumulate in the tissues of marine organisms, including shellfish (Hossain et al., 2023a). In 2021, the annual production of plastic products was 390.7 million metric tons while China is the largest plastics producer in the world producing more than 32% of the annual plastics production (Statista, 2023b). Around 10 million metric tons of plastic waste are produced each year and dumped into the ocean (Ruiz, 2023). Almost all the major river systems have already been polluted with MPs. For example, a recent study reported that globally, oceans are receiving plastics from 1000 MPs contaminated river runoffs (Parker, 2021). Unfortunately, most of the shellfish aquaculture farms are situated on the coasts and banks of the oceans, and rivers as the farming practices need available water sources. As a result, MPs from the polluted water are entering inside the shellfish culture system.

Shellfish aquaculture is a vital industry that contributes to food security, economic growth, and sustainable coastal development worldwide (FAO, 2020). Culture fisheries have been contributing more than capture fisheries in the last three decades (FAO, 2018). According to FAO (2022), more than 48% of production was sourced from culture fisheries in the year 2020, where marine aquaculture contributed 33.1 million tonnes. The report of FAO, (2022) also added that about 11,237 and 17,742 thousand tons of crustaceans and mollusks were produced from mariculture in 2022. In addition to providing a source of high-quality protein and essential nutrients for human consumption, shellfish aquaculture also generates employment and income opportunities for coastal communities, particularly in developing countries where alternative livelihoods may be limited. Among all the shellfish species, White leg shrimp (*Penaeus vannamei*), Red swamp crawfish (*Procambarus clarkia*), Chinese mitten crab (*Eriocheir sinensis*), Giant tiger prawn (*Penaeus monodon*), Indo-Pacific swamp crab (*Scylla serrata*), Giant River prawn (*Macrobrachium rosenbergii*), Oriental River prawn (*Macrobrachium nipponense*), Green mud crab (*Scylla paramamosain*) are the most farmed crustaceans (FAO, 2022). On the other hand, Cupped oysters (*Crassostrea* spp.), Japanese carpet shell (*Ruditapes philippinarum*) Scallops, Sea mussels, Constricted tagelus (*Sinonovacula constricta*), Pacific cupped oyster (*Magallana gigas*) Blood cockle (*Anadara granosa*), Chilean mussel (*Mytilus chilensis*) are most farmed mollusks globally (FAO, 2022). Shellfish consumption is increasing day by day, for instance, in 2018, the USA consumed more than 5.3 billion pounds of fish and shellfish (Statista, 2023a). In European countries, mussel farming (*Mytilus edulis*, and *Mytilus galloprovincialis*) contributes more

than 90% of total mussel landing and the farming technique is also expanding in Chile, and New Zealand (*The European Market for Mussels, 2023*). Conclusively, shellfish are an important source of food and livelihood for millions of people worldwide. For that reason, the potential risks associated with MPs in shellfish aquaculture have become a major concern.

In recent years, the effects of microplastics pollution on shellfish organisms have been thoroughly investigated. These investigations have shown multiple impacts of MPs particles on shellfish organisms including the growth, reproduction, and survival of shellfish, the accumulation of microplastics in their tissues, and the potential transfer of microplastics to humans through consumption that questions the safety of the products (LGA et al., 2018). For example, MPs can cause lower survival rate in blood clam, *Tegillarca granosa* (Tang et al., 2022), weight loss in giant river prawn, *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* (Jaikumar et al., 2021), liver damage in Chinese mitten crab *Eriocheir sinensis* (Yang et al., 2022), reproduction alterations in crayfish, *Procambarus clarkia* (Zhang et al., 2022), lower growth in the American lobster *Homarus americanus* (Woods et al., 2020), and changes in the inflammatory responses, and energy metabolism in pacific oyster, *Crassostrea gigas* (Teng et al., 2021). The above-mentioned shellfish organisms are valuable aquaculture products and the field investigation in their respective aquaculture practices reported that these organisms are already found with MPs inside their body (Teng et al., 2019; Hue et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2021; Do et al., 2022; Reunura & Prommi, 2022).

Disease outbreaks, higher mortality rates, poor growth performance, pollutant contamination, antibiotic resistance are the shellfish aquaculture challenges that are resulting in lower production, profit, and food security issues. This review paper has overviewed the MPs occurrence, their impact on shellfish aquaculture, possible threats, remedies, and human health complications. This study has also provided insight into the current state of knowledge on microplastics pollution in shellfish aquaculture. By summarizing the existing evidence, this review has identified some knowledge gaps and research priorities for future studies, as well as policy implications for the sustainable management of shellfish aquaculture in the face of microplastics pollution.

2. Methods:

By following the study of Yao et al. (2020) and Guo et al. (2019), the methodology of this study was prepared from the database of the Web of Science (WOS), a systematic, multidisciplinary, and comprehensive authoritative database. This review study was conducted by considering all of the published studies either review or article paper until 31st December' 2023 from the WOS database.

VOSviewer V1.6.19 was used to construct and visualize the bibliometric information and their networks. It is a widely used software that presents the networks among the researches, journals, and researchers by considering the data on keywords, affiliations, citations, co-citations, co-authorships, and bibliographic coupling. In this study, the construction of the literature's networking was conducted by following some systematic sequential steps.

The countries networks were only visualized in this study to show the country trends of MPs based shellfish study around the world. The keywords used in this study were, microplastics, shrimp, prawn, lobsters, crayfish/crawfish, crabs, clams, mussels, oysters, scallops, abalones, mollusks, crustaceans, shellfish, aquaculture, and mariculture. The specific shellfish groups used as keywords were selected following the study of Gardner et al. (2021); Kibenge (2022); and H. Yang et al. (2016) The keywords were chosen carefully to include all of the published literatures under the field of shellfish aquaculture and microplastics pollution.

Fig1: Bibliometric analysis stages for the extraction of published literature from the Web of Science (WOS) data base (until 2023).

Fig 2 presented the research trend in different countries based on the network, density visualization. A total of 90 countries have been recorded from the WOS database that conducted the studies on shellfish MPs pollution. To ensure the inclusion of all of the countries, the threshold of minimum documents per country was 1 and the minimum citation was 0.

a

VOSviewer

b

VOSviewer

Fig 2. Bibliometric analysis of the published literatures on Microplastics in Shellfish organisms, a) Network visualization of countries that published at least one paper. The same color of the nodes represent collaboration among the countries (cluster) and node size is related with the number of articles. b) Density visualization of the countries where the intensity of the color denotes the number of publications at certain countries.

China has the highest number of documents as per the Fig 2; node size (a) and density of the color (b). But when it is about the strength of the links among the countries published literatures and collaborations, Italy stands with maximum total link strength of 114, followed by France 112 and China 99. **Table 1.** showed here the top 10 countries with the maximum link strength.

Table 1: Top 10 countries having the maximum link strength based on their networking and collaboration with the other countries in co-authorship.

Country	Document	Total Link Strength
Italy	139	114
France	94	112
China	290	99
England	64	92
Germany	68	90
USA	108	83
Spain	81	78
Norway	39	77
Portugal	65	77
Canada	54	73

3. MPs Accumulation in Shellfish Aquaculture

In natural waterbodies, shellfish accumulate MPs particles due to their positions in the food web of ecosystem. Most of the shellfish are in the lower trophic level and they prey generally on phytoplankton and zooplankton. A recent study by Walkinshaw et al. (2020) on the trophic level and MPs proximity relationship reported shellfish are at higher risk of MPs contamination due to their lower trophic level position. However, in the aquaculture

system, MPs accumulation in shellfish occurs when the MPs particles are ingested by shellfish assuming them as food or they prey MPs contaminated organisms from the culture environment.

Many laboratory simulation experiments reported the accumulation of different size MPs by shellfish organisms. In the captive aquaculture, and the mariculture system shellfish consume either phytoplankton or zooplankton from their environment along with commercial feeds. The interesting fact is most of the phytoplankton and zooplankton are in the same size range of MPs particles. The planktons are generally 0.2 to a maximum of 4 mm in size (Brierley, 2017) and this is in the same size range as microplastic particles (1µm to 5mm) (Frias & Nash, 2019). So, the non-selective feeding mode of the farmed mollusks makes them more prone to the accidental accumulation MPs particles. A recent study on the universal plankton and MPs size survey included the phytoplankton and zooplankton in the microplastics size range while a few zooplanktons were not included in the MPs size range (Bermúdez & Swarzenski, 2021).

The trophic transfer of MPs particles is another way of MP's accumulation in the shellfish aquaculture system. Even all of the positions of the ecosystem (=trophic level) are already contaminated with MPs particles. In northeastern China, a study in the Laiohe estuary reported that, the occurrence of MPs particles in different trophic levels. That study found a trend of higher MPs detection (91.95%) ratio in the upper trophic level such as spotted-tail goby (*Synechogobius ommaturus*), redeye mullet (*Mugil gaimaregianus*), and seabass (*Lateolabrax japonicus*) than the other trophic level members (sandworm, mollusk, and crustaceans) (F. Wang et al., 2021). That is indicating the biomagnification of MPs particles although studies are still limited to support the biomagnification concept of MPs within the ecosystem. The feeding strategy of shellfish species makes them vulnerable to MPs pollution based on some recent studies. Shellfish organisms have different feeding behavior. Crustaceans are omnivores, detritivores, scavengers, predators, and filter feeders whereas mollusks are grazers, scavengers, filter feeders, scrapers, and predators. MPs accumulation inside the shellfish body is directly linked with this feeding behavior as it leads to the route of MPs accumulation. Non-selective feeding methods such as suspension, filter, and deposit feeders are prone to accumulate MPs particles (Wesch et al., 2016). Comparatively, selective feeders (such as crabs, lobsters, shrimps) can easily ignore the accidental ingestion of any non-food particles. Therefore, the route of MPs accumulation for them is bioaccumulation through predation of contaminated organisms (Murray & Cowie, 2011). Recently FAO, (2022) reported about 16 commercially important shellfish that contribute more than 80% of the total production of shellfish aquaculture globally. The

alarming fact is almost all of the shellfish organisms have been found contaminated with MPs in many recent investigations (**Figure: 3**).

* (FAO, 2022); ** (Pérez et al., 2020); (Ukhrowi et al., 2021), (Martinelli et al., 2020), (Wang et al., 2021), (Scott et al., 2019), (Sui et al., 2020), (Liu et al., 2021), (Gladys Jambre, 2021), (Reunura & Prommi, 2022), (Hossain et al., 2020), (McGoran et al., 2020), (Zhang et al., 2021), (Reunura & Prommi, 2022), (Valsan et al., 2024); Here: N.S.Y= Not studied yet

Figure 3: World shellfish aquaculture production of the 8 major crustacean and mollusk species in 2020 and the evidence of their contamination with MPs particles

Recently four (4) farmed shellfish were investigated for the MPs accumulation. Shrimp *Penaeus hardwickii* was the lowest in accumulating MPs whereas the suspension feeder, razor clam (*Sinonovacula constricta*), and oyster (*Ostrea denselamellosa*) were detected with higher MPs (Wu et al., 2020). In the shellfish hatchery operations microalgae are either used as feed for culturing zooplanktons, *Artemia* (Bhuvaneshwari et al., 2018; Martelli et al., 2020), or rotifer (Kandathil Radhakrishnan et al., 2020) to use them as larvae feed or they are used as supplementary with zooplanktons to balance the shellfish larvae nutrition (Jaseera et al., 2021).

Figure 4: MPs accumulation pathway in the shellfish aquaculture system with their potential trophic transfers

MPs-microalgae interactions is a concern for shellfish hatcheries as the microplastics attached to toxic chemical contaminants (de Wilt et al., 2016; Zhou et al., 2014) can easily enter the microalgae cells (Sutherland & Ralph, 2019) and the trophic transfer ensure their existence in the shellfish body (Ahmadi et al., 2022). MPs accumulation was also reported in the laboratory conditions for some artemia species such as *Artemia parthenogenetica* (Zhang, et al., 2019), *Artemia franciscana* (Kokalj et al., 2018), and *Artemia salina* (Jeyavani et al., 2022), also in rotifer

species *Brachionus plicatilis* (Lan et al., 2021). Trophic transfers can easily let MPs particles enter the hatchery-raised shellfish larvae. **Figure 4.** Illustrated the potential routes of MPs accumulation in shellfish aquaculture practices such as feeding mode, the trophic transfer (via prey), and even through commercial feeds (C. Yao et al., 2021). The contamination of MPs in the farmed shellfish through the potential routes has been reported in several studies. The evidence of MPs particles in shellfish aquaculture systems is stated in **Table.2.**

Table 2: Global evidence of MPs accumulation in the shellfish aquaculture system

Location	Sample source	MPs Abundance	MPs types	Source	References
Seventeen (17) coastal aquaculture sites in China	<i>Crassostrea gigas</i> , <i>C. hongkongensis</i> , <i>C. angulate</i> , and <i>C. sikamea</i>	0.62 items/g (wet weight)	CP, PE, PET, PA, PVC, PC, and PS	Atmospheric transportation, WWTP effluents, tourism, fishing	(Teng et al., 2019)
Clam aquaculture farm, Vietnam	<i>Meretrix lyrata</i> , <i>Tapes dorsatus</i>	0.53 items/g (wet weight)	PE, PET, nylon, PP, EVA	N/A	(Hue et al., 2021)
Mariculture, Maowei sea China	Water Oyster	1.47 to 7.61 items/L 7.05 items/g (gills), 2.84 items/g (digestive glands)	PE, PET, nylon, PP, PS, PU, PBT, and, POM	Riverine emissions, land-based sources, fishery activities	(Zhu et al., 2021)
Shrimp Culturing farm, Southeast China	Water	1594 items/m ³	PE, PET, PP, PS, PA, PC, and polyacrylic acid (PAA).	Feeding bags, nearest aquaculture activities, anthropogenic activities, fishing nets, fishing ropes, river runoff, and black waterproof	(Chen et al., 2020)
Oyster Farming Area, Vietnam	<i>C. gigas</i>	1.88 items/g (wet weight)	Nylon, MUF, EVOH, PTFE, PEI, PVA, PP, cellophane, PAI, LDPE, and UF	Textiles, aquaculture activities, port activities,	(Do et al., 2022)
Shrimp polyculture pond, Central Thailand	<i>Macrobrachium rosenbergii</i> ,	GI tract Male: 32.66 items/g Female: 32.14 items/g,	PE, polyvinyl alcohol, polycaprolactone, acrylonitrile butadiene styrene,	Culture water, fishing gear, and shrimp meal	(Reunura & Prommi, 2022)

	<i>Litopenaeus vannamei</i>	11.00 items/g,			
Mariculture water, Longjiao Bay, China	Shrimp meal (feed of shrimp aquaculture)	10.7 items/100g	PES, paraffin wax, PE, and rayon	Waste yarn of textiles	(C. Yao et al., 2021)
Aquaculture site, Xiangshan Bay, China	Oyster: (<i>Ostrea denselamellosa</i>), Razor clam: (<i>Sinonovacula constricta</i>) Shrimp: (<i>Parapenaeopsis hardwickii</i>),	0.31 items/g (wet weight) 0.21 items/g (wet weight) 0.25 items/g (wet weight)	Cellulose, PP, PA, PET, and PE	Water and sediment of Bay,	(Wu et al., 2020)
Shrimp farm, Zuhai city, China	Sediment White leg shrimp (<i>Litopenaeus vannamei</i>)	5129 items/kg 14.08 items/g (wet weight)	Cellulose, PE, cotton, acrylic, PET, PP, PA, and PS	Shrimp culture activities, plastic industry, cosmetic industry	(Yan et al., 2021)
Bang Bo Aquaculture Farm, Thailand	Blood Cockles (<i>Tegillarca granosa</i>)	6 items/individual	PP, PE, PES, PVC, PA, and co-polymer	Packaging materials, transportation materials, cosmetic products, household plastics, grocery bags	(Ta et al., 2022)
Siracha Fisheries research center aquaculture farm, Thailand	Green mussel (<i>Perna viridis</i>)	11 items/individual	PP, PE, PES, PVC, and PA	Packaging materials, transportation materials, cosmetic products, household plastics, grocery bags	(Ta et al., 2022)
Mariculture in Bohai and Yellow Sea	Pacific Oyster <i>Crassostrea gigas</i>	2.4 items/L (winter), 3.28 items/L (autumn), 0.22 items/L (spring), 0.45 items/L (summer)	PET, PE, PA, PP, CP	Environmental factors, Human activities,	(Du et al., 2022)

		Surface seawater	3.41 to 8.86 items/L			
Mud (<i>Scylla</i> sp.)	Crab	Water	127.92 items/100 L	PE, PS, PP, and Nylon	Packaging materials, transportation materials, cosmetic products, household plastics, grocery bags	(Hossain, et al., 2023a)
Aquaculture system		Sediment	7.5 particles/g			

Note: CP: Cellophane, PE: polyethylene, PET: polyethylene terephthalate, PA: polyamide, PVC: polyvinyl chloride, PC: polycarbonate, PS: polystyrene, EVA: ethylene-vinyl acetate copolymer, PU: polyether urethane, PBT: polybutylene terephthalate, POM: polyoxymethylene, PAA: polyacrylic acid, MUF: melamine-urea-formaldehyde resin, EVOH; ethylene vinyl alcohol, PTFE: polytetrafluoroethylene, PVA: polyvinyl alcohol, PAI: polyamine-imide, LDPE: low density polyethylene, UF: poly-urea-formaldehyde, PEI: polyethyleneimine and PES: polyester

4. Impact of MPs on the Farmed Shellfish Organisms

The increasing trend of shellfish aquaculture production is significant and it is around 19.75 million metric tons to 28.978 million metric tons (FAO, 2022; World Fisheries and Aquaculture, 2012). FAO, (2022) reported that shellfish aquaculture is contributing more than the captured source in the daily shellfish food demand. But the pollution events like MPs occurrence and inorganic chemical intrusions are raising the issue of food safety. More than one-decade old study raised the issue of antibiotic resistance, organic pollutants, pathogenic bacteria, viruses, metals, parasites, etc. related to aquaculture (Sapkota et al., 2008) which is still an ongoing issue for the industry. Among these pollutants, MPs particles particularly gain special attention in aquaculture as there are still no control measures considered yet. It is still being addressed as an emerging threat to aquaculture practices (Wu et al., 2023) although the detrimental impact of MPs pollution has already been found in aquaculture products (Hossain et al., 2023).

When MPs particles are exposed to the shellfish organisms, their innate immune system is triggered after they pass through the mechanical and chemical barriers of the body (Yang & Li, 2023). The innate immunity triggering initiates the activity of innate immune mechanisms like effector cells activity such as macrophage, lymphoid cells, and mast cell response (Murphy et al., 2022) resulting in some behavioral changes that result from the cellular level response mechanism where the cellular functions for the MPs particles are directed from the molecular level,

particularly gene expressions. There are two possible and potential ways of MPs-derived toxicity to the exposed shellfish, i) MPs causing toxicity, ii) MPs sorption of biological, and chemical contaminants causing toxicity.

4.1. MPs causing toxicity

In order to understand the toxicities of MPs particles in the shellfish organisms, the MPs exposure treatment in the laboratory condition has been found as a potential technique. Because the natural environment is an uncontrolled condition and numerous stressors such as chemical contaminants, bacteria, parasites, environmental parameters fluctuations are always influencing the shellfish growth. Fig 5. has illustrated the classification shellfish organisms.

Fig 5: Classification of Shellfish organisms according to (Woo & Bahna, 2011)

In the laboratory simulation studies of MPs challenge-impact tests, the commercially important shellfish are exposed to environmentally relevant MPs concentrations to examine their response mechanism. The environmentally relevant concentration (ERC) of MPs is the abundance of MPs particles that have already been found in the environment of any particular organism. The majority of studies have demonstrated the negative effects of MPs on shellfish organisms at levels higher than the ERC, which poses a significant barrier to challenge-

impact-based MP research. According to a recent assessment of MPs exposure in aquatic organisms, 82% of MP challenge-impact tests employed greater MP particle dosages than the actual concentration in the environment. (Cunningham & Sigwart, 2019). Because of this, the majority of impact studies are now being debated by academics worldwide. However, it is undeniable that MPs particles continue to have some negative impacts on the ERC of MPs particles in shellfish organisms. The majority of research employ the acute dose MPs exposure experiment to assess the immediate impact of greater concentrations of MPs particles. To date, several farmed shellfish organisms such as mussels, shrimp, crabs, lobsters, crayfish have been exposed to MPs in laboratory conditions.

4.1.1. Mussel

The impact of MPs particles on mussels has been thoroughly studied as they have ecological and commercial importance in the aquaculture sector (Abelouah et al., 2023; FAO, 2022). The proximity of MPs particles in mussels is higher because of their feeding mood as studies reported that filter feeders are more prone to be contaminated with MPs particles (Urbina et al., 2023). *Mytilus galloprovincialis* also known as Mediterranean mussel is an important aquaculture organism in Eastern Atlantic and Mediterranean regions (Bonham et al., 2022). The MPs exposure treatments of the Mediterranean mussel have been thoroughly conducted by (Avio et al., 2015; Capolupo et al., 2018; Cappello et al., 2021; Choi et al., 2022; Fernández et al., 2022) for the MPs PE, PS, PET, and HDPE. MPs were found to cause alterations in hemolymph, gills, digestive tissue, marked accumulation of pyrene, cellular effects, peroxisomal proliferation, lysosomal compartment, antioxidant system, genotoxicity, immunological disorders, gene expression alterations (Avio et al., 2015). The exposure of MPs to 50 to 500 MPs particles/L has led to gene upregulations for the biogenesis of the shell. The study found lysosomal enzyme production was ceased for the coding alterations, and modulation in the immune system (Capolupo et al., 2018). On the other hand, disturbance in osmotic imbalance, amino acid metabolism, energy metabolism, and antioxidant properties due to the changes of their respective metabolic pathways related to changes in the metabolite's productions or insolvency was also noticed (Cappello et al., 2021). Even the exposure of PET MPs at environmentally relevant concentrations caused testosterone, and estradiol consequences a reduction in the gonadal size (Choi et al., 2022). The same study showed some oxidative stresses, digestive gland disorder, and neurotoxicity when the species were exposed to a higher than environmentally relevant concentration of PET particles. The thick-shelled mussel *Mytilus coruscus* has been investigated for its response toward PS MPs

particles (Wang et al., 2020). In that study, the digestive enzymes were found to be affected most in response to MPs along with increased antioxidant enzymes catalase, and glutathione activity. Later on, the same MPs were found to impair the byssal attachment of *Mytilus coruscus* mussel which was confirmed in the gene expression of mussel's foot protein and collagen protein alterations (Shang et al., 2021). The byssus is a rootlike 30 to 50 fiber consisting thick ribbon of some organism of phylum Mollusca which is made up of complex protein molecules and helps the organism to be attached to substrates (Beninger & Le Pennec, 2016). The byssal strength was reduced to 50% along with its production for another commercially important mussel called blue mussel, *Mytilus edulis* when it was exposed to PE, and biodegradable PLA MPs. The metabolic, detoxifying, immune, and structural proteins were affected more by PE exposure than PLA MPs in the same study (Green et al., 2019). A similar investigation for PE and biodegradable PHB MPs found biodegradable PHB MPs were more deleterious to blue mussel than synthetic PE exposure (Magara et al., 2019). Gut microbiota status for HDPE MPs exposure in *Mytilus edulis* and about 125 operational taxonomic units (OTU) were found to be altered due to the MPs exposure (Li et al., 2020). The operational taxonomic unit (OTU) is a term widely used in the field of microbial ecology for bacterial studies having a 97% similarity index in sequences after the 16s rDNA sequencing (He et al., 2015).

4.1.2. Oyster

Oyster is one of the major edible bivalves and mostly cultured (FAO, 2022) species of the mollusk group. *Crassostrea gigas* also known as the Pacific oyster, is a commercially important culture species (B. H. Park et al., 1988) and has been thoroughly experimented with under different MPs exposure. Between PE and PET microplastics, PET has been found more toxic although both MP exposures resulted in the inhibition of lipid metabolism, changes in the inflammatory responses, and energy metabolism (Teng et al., 2021). The study by Bringer et al., (2021) reported that exposure to HDPE caused the shell growth reduction of *C. gigas*, increased the number of valve micro-closure, and decreased the duration of valve opening. On the other hand, a baseline study by (Corami et al., 2020) used *C. gigas* as a model organism for the small MPs ingestion studies that predicted that <100 µm MPs may block the intestinal passage of the organism for food. Another Pacific oyster species *Magallana gigas* has been found to release 84.6% PS microplastics after 72 hours and the rest were found in the shell cavity (Graham et al., 2019). The embryonic and larval development of Jinjiang oyster *Crassostrea rivularis* was affected by the commercial MPs although the study did not find any oxidative stress on the larval developmental stages (Sui et al., 2022).

4.1.3. Clam

Commercially important clams such as the blood clams, the manila clam, the peppery furrow shell, the wedge clam, the surf clam, the Asian clam, etc. have been studied for MPs impacts analysis as these bivalves have aquaculture and ecological value (Parra et al., 2021; Tan et al., 2020; Louzán A et al., 2016; Srisomwong et al., 2018; Network Of Aquaculture Centres In Asia, 1988). Blood clam, *Tegillarca granosa* showed a significantly reduced survival rate, induced reactive oxygen species (ROS), and stifled the gene expression from the mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK), and actin cytoskeleton pathways on PS exposure (Tang et al., 2022). The MPs exposure was also found to affect the energy supply and detoxification process of blood clam (Zhang et al., 2022). Manila clam, *Ruditapes philippinarum*, is the world's second most commercially important cultured mollusk (Tan et al., 2020). A recent study showed, that on PS exposure, the species responded with increased respiration, excretion, decreased absorption efficiency, and energy availability which led to poor growth, and reproduction efficiency (Jiang et al., 2022). The same species showed no oxidative stress on PE MPs exposure but it reduced the rate of filtration, influenced the immune system, and altered the histology of gill, and digestive glands. (Sikdokur et al., 2020). Ribeiro et al., (2017), and O'Donovan et al., (2020) conducted a study on *Scrobicularia plana*, they found Oxidative stress, neurotoxicity, Gill damage, antioxidant potentials, and DNA damage on PS and PE exposure. MPs particles also affected the Asian clam, *Corbicula fluminea* (Yusof et al., 2020), *Macraa veneriformis* (X. Zhang et al., 2021), *Meretrix* (Luan et al., 2019), and *Donax trunculus* (Tlili et al., 2020).

4.1.4. Other Mollusks:

Disc abalone and webfoot octopus are two commercially important aquaculture species (J. Park et al., 2008; Zheng et al., 2023). Disc abalone species *Haliotis discus hannai*, and webfoot octopus' species *Amphioctopus fangsiao* were introduced to MPs fibers and PS microplastics respectively. In both cases, DNA damages, and oxidative stresses were noticed in the exposed organisms. Another farmed mollusk freshwater snail was exposed to polypropylene (PP) microplastics that caused oxidative damages of lipid, and protein, alteration of neural activities, and activities of digestive enzymes (Garr et al., 2011; Jeyavani & Vaseeharan, 2023). On the other hand, exposure to PE microplastics of another freshwater snail species, *Pomacea canaliculata* enhanced the shell generation and related enzymes (Lopes et al., 2023).

4.1.5. Shrimp and Prawn

Shrimp are mostly cultured shellfish in the world particularly the whiteleg shrimp, *Penaeus (Litopenaeus) vannamei* (FAO, 2022). The MPs pollution in their culture system has been reported in many studies (Table 2) and the potential impact was also investigated in many laboratory challenge experiments. The PS microplastics

have been found to make stress in *L. vannamei* as evidenced by the gill vacuolization, gill deformation, and oxidative stress by increasing the gene expression of superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), heat shock protein 70 & 90 (HSP70, HSP90), thioredoxin (trx), alteration of carbon lipids, amino acids, and carbohydrates metabolism (Xing et al., 2023). PS MPs particles ranging from 0.1 to 20 μm also influenced gut microbiome diversity of the same species which was highlighted by the higher alpha diversity (mean species diversity) in a correlation with some metabolic pathways such as proline and arginine metabolism, absorption, and digestion of protein, and degradation of lysine (N. Zhou et al., 2023). Even the detrimental effect of MPs on gut microbiota has been found irrespective of their exposure duration. The existence of MPs in the surrounding environment either for a short duration (Z. Wang et al., 2021) or long duration (N. Zhou et al., 2023) caused changes in the gut microbiome that have a significant role in the shellfish health (Holt et al., 2021). The MPs have been found to affect the reproductive hormones of shrimp. The gonado-somatic index (GSI) was shortened which was confirmed by the transcriptional study. There was an upregulation of GIH (gonad-inhibiting hormone), and MIH (molt-inhibiting hormone) hormones that are related to the development of gonads in *L. vannamei* (Han et al., 2022). The freshwater shrimp *Neocaridina palmata* which is abundant in Vietnam and China has been found to take MPs particles PE, and PVC, with their foods regardless of their different shapes (Klein et al., 2021). On PS and PE exposure, the giant river prawn, *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* responded negatively by lower survival rate, body lengths, and weights along with the increasing antioxidant enzymes (Jaikumar et al., 2021). The testicular dysfunction, immune stress, lower survival rate, lower hatching success, and even the lower survival rate and immunity in the first generation of the exposed berried prawns were detected for the oriental freshwater prawn, *Macrobrachium nipponese* when they were exposed to PS MPs particles (Sun et al., 2022).

4.1.6. Other Crustaceans

Crustacean organisms that are cultured other than shrimps, and prawn mainly crab, lobster, and crayfish, have been studied for the different MPs exposure-based impacts. The crab species that are affected by MPs has been reported are *Callinectes sapidus*, *Charybdis japonica*, *Eriocheir sinensis*, *Pagurus bernhardus*, *Minuca ecuadoriensis*, *Petrolisthes laevigatus*, *Emerita analoga*, *Ucides cordatus*, etc. Upon exposure to MPs of different types, these species have responded negatively such as heavy metal accumulation (Munuera et al., 2021), collapsed antioxidant defense mechanism, collapsed detoxification capacity (Wang et al., 2021), behavioral influence during shell selection (McDaid et al., 2023 Horn et al., 2020), lower survival rate (Villegas et al., 2022), weight loss, nutritional damage (Urbina et al., 2023), and poor defense mechanism (Nobre et al., 2022). The Chinese mitten crab (*Eriocheir sinensis*) has been noticeably studied for microplastic exposure-based impact

studies due to their higher culture and economic value, particularly in China (Wang et al., 2016). The Chinese mitten crab has responded with inflammation, oxidative damage, liver damage, increased antioxidant capacity, immune system, and gut microbiome fluctuations from biochemical, and gene expression levels (Yang et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2019).

Procambarus clarkia is a commercially important crayfish and the studies on the species reported fluctuations in gut microbiota, immune stress, oxidative stress, bioaccumulation, alterations in antioxidant enzymes, immune genes alterations, interference with transcription, altered translation, degradation of protein, metabolism of lipid, downregulated expression for vitellogenin, and reproduction alterations (Zhang et al., 2022; Xiao et al., 2022; Zeng et al., 2023; Capanni et al., 2021). Even with the lipid synthesis cessation in hepatopancreas, intracellular fatty acids utilization was affected by MPs contamination which stressed the growth in *Cherax quadricarinatus* (Chen et al., 2020). The latest study on freshwater crayfish, *Astacus leptodactylus* reported that cellular chemicals like glucose, enzymes, cholesterol, and triglycerides can be affected by PE MPs contamination whereas the cellular components like hyaline cells, total hemocytes, semi-granular cells, and percentages of granular cells were also found to be affected (Gholamhosseini et al., 2023). American lobster *Homarus americanus* larvae have been recently exposed to PET MPs which resulted in lower oxygen consumption, higher molting time, and lower growth (Woods et al., 2020). The impacts of MPs particles on crustacean organisms need to be investigated more as the information on their responses toward MPs is still insufficient.

4.2. MPs sorption of biological, and chemical contaminants causing toxicity

MPs are generally sourced from various anthropogenic activities such as household activities, manufacturing industries, tourism, treatment plants, etc. (**Figure: 4**). On the other hand, the organic and inorganic pollutants are sourced from insecticides, herbicides, flame retardants, surfactants, plasticizers, illicit drugs, antifouling agents, pharmaceuticals, byproducts of different chemical products, antibiotics, fragrances, day care products, fossil fuels, mining activities, etc. (Hange & Awofolu, 2017). No matter from where the MPs, organic and inorganic pollutants are discharged or released, their ultimate destination is the ocean (O'Donovan et al., 2018). In the waterbodies, these chemical discharges make a distinct interaction that is led by the MPs particles by a process called sorption. When any chemical transfers from a fluid to a solid through adsorption or absorption it is called sorption (Fu et al., 2021). The adsorption occurs in low organic pollutant concentrations that lead the MPs to exert the forces of lipophilicity and also their higher surface area (lipophilicity). On the other absorption occurs at higher chemical concentrations (Hartmann et al., 2017) but it is difficult to distinguish the ways of sorption because of their simultaneous actions in the environment. The study on MPs-organic and inorganic pollutants as in separate studies

are found to exist and toxic to aquaculture (Harmon, 2015; Hidayati et al., 2021; Emenike et al., 2022). A recent study found MPs particles PP, PE, HDPE, and PVC with organic pollutants polychlorinated bisphenol and dioxins in blue mussel cage farming (Abihssira-García et al., 2022) whereas some pharmaceuticals like ibuprofen, florfenicol, oxytetracycline, roxithromycin, venlafaxine, etc. were also found carried by MPs (Santos et al., 2021). Some other MPs like LDPE, PET, nylon, PVC, PUR, POM, PS, and PP were found with heavy metals, Cu, Zn, Cd, and Pb from the urban regions of British Columbian, Canada (Munier & Bendell, 2018). **Table 3.** has showed in details about the sorption of different chemicals with MPs in the shellfish organism's body.

Table 3: Effects of MPs adsorbed different pollutants (Organic, and inorganic) on different shellfish organisms

Shellfish Organisms	MPs	MPs adsorbed chemical contaminants	Types of pollutants	Effects on Organisms	References
<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>	PS	Cadmium Benzopyrene	Heavy metal Organic pollutant	Cellular alterations of digestive glands	(von Hellfeld et al., 2022)
<i>Mytilus coruscus</i>	PS	Florfenicol, oxytetracycline, sulfamethoxazole	Antibiotics	Immunotoxicity	(Han et al., 2021)
<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>	PS	Naphthenic North Sea crude oil	Organic pollutant	Alterations in enzyme activity	(González-Soto et al., 2022)
<i>Corbicula fluminea</i>	PS	Cd	Heavy metal	Affected gills, and gonad; Antagonism in digestive glands	(Parra et al., 2021)
<i>Litopenaeus vannamei</i>	PS	Bisphenol A	Organic pollutant	Affected gonadal development	(Han et al., 2022)
<i>Tegillarca granosa</i>	PS	Bisphenol A	Organic pollutant	Alterations in chemotactic activity, induced ROS, and hemocyte's protein carbonyl, cessation of the MAPK, and actin	(Tang et al., 2022)

				cytoskeleton regulation pathway	
<i>Tegillarca granosa</i>	PS	Tetrabromobisphenol A	Organic pollutant	Reduced adenosine triphosphate, phosphofructokinase, and lower pyruvate kinase due to the disruption in detoxification process	(W. Zhang et al., 2022)
<i>Minuca ecuadoriensis</i>	HDPE	Malathion	Organophosphate insecticide	Lower survival rate	(Villegas et al., 2022)
<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>	HDPE	chlorpyrifos	Organophosphate pesticide	Negative biological response	(Fernández et al., 2022)
<i>Mytilus edulis</i>	PE	Fluoranthene	Organic pollutant	Oxidative stress of organism	(Magara et al., 2018)
<i>Crassostrea gigas</i>	HDPE	Chlortoluron	Organic pollutant	Reduced shell growth	(Bringer et al., 2021)
<i>Ucides cordatus</i>	PE	Triclosan	Antibiotic	DNA damage, lipid peroxidation, glutathione reduction	(Nobre et al., 2022)

The effects on the shellfish organisms due to the MPs and their related toxicities are further demonstrated in **Figure 6.** by showing the cellular responses.

Fig. 6: Cellular responses of shellfish organisms to exposure to MPs and sorbates (antibiotics, heavy metals, insecticides, and pathogenic bacteria).

5. Rising Challenges and possible remedies for shellfish aquaculture

Recent studies coined a term for MPs particles for their sorption abilities of other nano chemicals or pollutants, which is ‘trojan horse’ meaning ‘hot pockets of contaminant transport’ (Adkisson, 2020). So microplastics alone or MPs- adsorbate together can cause many complications in the contaminated organisms. The trojan horse effect of MPs particles has been recently reviewed by Hu et al., (2022) and the study mentioned some contaminants, like heavy metals (Cd, Pb, Cu, Zn, Mn, Ni), POPs (fluoranthene, phenanthrene, trichlorobenzenes, pentachloro benzenes, Hexachlorobenzene, trifluralin, imidacloprid, buprofezin, and carbofuran, carbendazim), pathogenic bacteria (*Actinobacter baumannii*, *Afpia broomeae*, *Pseudomonas arguina*, *Escherichia coli*, *Vibrio pseudoalteromonas*, *Flavobacterium*, *Vibrio cholera*, and *Pseudoalteromonas*). These contaminants are raising different possible challenges for shellfish aquaculture systems both for import and export businesses, and culture operations difficulties. The heavy metals and POPs generally create complexities in the shellfish export-import business. For example, a recent study on blue crabs found 7,262 mg/kg of Cd while they were experimented adsorbed with chronically exposed MPs particles (Hernández-López & Romero, 2022), and this level is beyond

the allowable limit of Cd, 0.5mg/kg for crustaceans according to the regulations for imported shellfish products from the Commission of the European Communities, (2006) in their revised version of 1st March 2023. So, this blue crab species cannot be traded in any EU country due to the export-import non-compliance condition. From the aquaculture activities perspective, antibiotic and bacterial contaminants make critical conditions for the culture system resulting in antibiotic resistance and disease widespread. In a recent study in a mariculture farm in Shandong, China, three bacteria, *Vibrio*, *Ruegeria*, and *Muricauda* resistance to tetracycline, penicillin, sulfafurazole, and erythromycin were detected at 6.40×10^6 to 2.48×10^8 cfu/g count that was maximum 5000 times to the water sample (Zhang et al., 2020). The antibiotic resistance in aquaculture derived from regular MPs contamination events has been thoroughly discussed by researchers (Lu et al., 2019; Cholewińska et al., 2022; Li et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2021; Dong et al., 2021) Because shellfish organisms are frequently exposed to MPs particles in their aquaculture system (**Table 3**), antibiotic resistance is increasing in these organisms. As a result, disease outbreaks that cause farming difficulties and human health issues are a big threat from MPs pollution (Elmahdi et al., 2016).

The possible remedies for MPs and their derived contamination are still under investigations as all the potential technologies innovated cannot remove them 100% from the environment in a large-scale application. The possible route of MPs in shellfish aquaculture is either the incoming water stocked for culturing or the use of plastics in the culture operations. Here, three control measures have been discussed to avoid MPs in the shellfish aquaculture system, i) treating water to remove MPs before stocking for culture, ii) using alternative plastics products in the shellfish aquaculture system, iii) ecological concept of reducing MPs pollution, and iv) International and regional policies and regulations

5.1. Treating water to remove MPs before stocking for culture

Conditioning of aquatic organisms before introducing them to the culture or country is commonly known as the bio-security approach. The level of water pollution due to MPs particles is now to such an extent that, it is now a matter of time to establish a MPs removal-water treatment plant in the aquafarms as a first-line contaminants defense system. MPs particle removal from water has been conducted through various treatment processes such as chemicals, and mechanical and biological approaches. So far, the technologies have been applied in many areas of research are MPs adsorption on microalgae, photocatalytic degradation, membrane separation approach, activated sludge treatment, biodegradation, and coagulation (Abuwatfa et al., 2021). **Table 4.** has presented the treatments and their efficiency in different fields when applied.

Table 4: Different MPs removal technologies practiced in the laboratory and industry level (PE= polyethylene, PET= polyethylene terephthalate, PS= polystyrene, PP= polypropylene, PVC= polyvinylchloride, PMMA= poly(methyl methacrylate), PA= polyamide, LDPE= low density polyethylene, PES= polyester, PLA= polylactide)

Treatment Process	Treatment type/Ingredients	Removal efficiency	Water Source	References
Coagulation	Ferrate (FeCl ₃ : NaOCl = 5:1)	>98% PE, and PET	Laboratory-prepared water and River surface water	(Lee et al., 2023)
	Al-based salt			(W. Wang et al., 2023)
	Fe-based salt	92.7% PS 91.2% PS	Laboratory prepared water	
Electro-coagulation	Al- anode	93.2% PE 91.7% PMMA 98.2% PP	Laboratory prepared water	(Shen et al., 2022)
Electrocoagulation- Electroflotation	Al-Fe electrode	100% PE, PVC	Wastewater treatment plant	(Akarsu et al., 2021)
	Fe-Al electrode	98% MPs	Laundry wastewater	(Akarsu & Deniz, 2020)
Membrane filtration	Polyvinylidene fluoride hydrophobic membrane (47mm, 0.22µm)	100% PE, PVC	Wastewater treatment plant	(Akarsu et al., 2021)
		>96% PE, PA	Laboratory simulation of	(Shen et al., 2021)

	Aluminosilicate membrane		wastewater treatment plant' water	
Adsorption	Magnetic carbon nanotubes	100% PE, PET, PA	Laboratory-made aqueous solution	(Y. Tang et al., 2021)
Sedimentation	Activated Sludge	40.7% MPs	Wastewater treatment plant	(X. Liu et al., 2019)
Biofloc bacteria	<i>Bacillus licheniformes</i>	43% PVC		
		20% PE		(Hossain et al., 2023a)
	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp.			
		21% LDPE	Carbon-free liquid bacteria culture media	
	<i>B. cereus</i>			
		35.72% LDPE		
	<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>			(Thakur et al., 2023)
		18.4% LDPE		
Agglomeration	Alkyltrichlorosilanes, organosilanes	13-99% PE, 7-99% PP, 40-76% PES, 65.2-93% PA, 30-80% PVC	Distilled and demineralized water	(Sturm et al., 2020) (Sturm et al., 2021)
Biofilter	Stone wool, filtralite, gravel	79% MPs	Wastewater treatment plant	(F. Liu et al., 2020)
Microalgae	<i>Scenedesmus abundans</i>	>84% PS, PMMA, PLA	Laboratory Prepared water simulating wastewater effluents	(Cheng & Wang, 2022)

Coagulation-flotation/flocculation processes such as coagulation, electrocoagulation, and density separation, are commonly and widely practiced MPs removal strategies for any water type (Rodríguez-Narvaez et al., 2021). Recently some innovations have also been added to the MPs removal strategies as the above-mentioned treatments have some drawbacks. A recent study applied a magnetic nano-Fe₃O₄ removal system where the removal efficiency was impressive, PE (86.87 ± 6.92%), PP (85.05 ± 4.70%), PS (86.11 ± 6.21%) but the PET removal rate was 62.83 ± 8.34% which was a bit lower to consider as an effective removal efficiency (Shi et al., 2022). Another study by Wang et al., (2022) approached a new sustainable technology to remove MPs with solar energy which was a promising attempt although the MPs collection efficiency was quite lower than the other methods. The use of poly (2-ethylhexyl acrylate) coated ZrSiO₄ beads as an adhesive has been found to remove more than 99% PS particles of 10µm in size (Chazovachii et al., 2021). The holey Ti₃-C₂ Tx membrane (nanosheet) can also remove 99.3% PS from wastewater which is a vacuum filtration approach (L. Yang et al., 2022). Above all these technologies, scientists are now more focused on the biodegradation approach of MPs due to its waste-free endpoint. But the only drawback of this technology is the lower MPs removal efficiency that is determined by the MPs weight loss rate. For example, a maximum molecular weight reduction of 40.1 ± 8.5% for PE MPs by mealworms (Brandon et al., 2018). On the other hand, the bacteria consortium has been found to reduce the maximum 21% weight of PE MPs in another study (Yin et al., 2020). Until any sustainable approaches are industrially established, conventional approaches for MPs removal can be used, as they can be removed at a higher rate, but the generation of waste and their disposal management should be considered.

5.2. Using alternative plastic products in the shellfish aquaculture practices

Plastics are commonly used in shellfish aquaculture practices due to their higher durability, hydrophobicity, lightweight, cheaper price, availability, and insulation properties. The possible alternative to plastics can be wooden or metal products but they don't have the above-mentioned characteristics. For example, in an online e-commerce platform in Malaysia, the price of a 10L plastic bucket is 5.80 USD whereas an alternative plastic product, a metal bucket price is 10.52 USD which is almost double in price. As a result, farmers are using plastic products without taking into account the consequences of poor disposal practices. More than a decade ago, green plastics usage alternative to plastics was highlighted in a study but 12 years later the usage of them is still rare (Kuruppallil, 2011). The usage of bioplastics was expected to replace synthetic plastics (Gill, 2014) but bioplastics are also found as another polluting agent in many studies (Qin et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2021; Green et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2021). So far, the alternative plastics usage strategy cannot work at the farmer's level until new

alternatives are approached. The inventions for searching for an alternative to plastics are still in infancy although bamboo, and sugarcane-derived tableware (Liu et al., 2020), and agriculture-derived cellulosic fractions for plastics alternative (Janaswamy et al., 2022) are initiatives for future considerations.

5.3. Ecological concept of reducing MPs pollution

A recent study by Wu et al., (2023) highlighted the mangrove area as a suitable location for establishing aquaculture practices while providing some potential MPs remediation measures. Mangrove area acts as a biotreatment plant for wastewater received from aquaculture and other land-based activities (Ouyang & Guo, 2016). Microplastics are generally trapped more in the mangrove regions due to the localization of dumping zones, more proximity to urban areas, and the structure of the mangrove ecosystem (Deng et al., 2021). Mangrove ecosystem structure particularly the roots of diversified plants (Horstman et al., 2015) their related fauna diversity, and microbiota resulting in the fragmentation of large plastics into the MPs (Luo et al., 2021). This in-situ fragmentation is well evident (Auta et al., 2022) and is one of the sources of MPs particles in mangrove areas (Deng et al., 2021). Higher concentration of MPs in the mangrove areas compared to the other ecosystems has proved that they are trapping zones for MPs particles (X. Liu et al., 2022; G. Tang et al., 2018). Researchers emphasized the critical situation of the mangrove ecosystem for MPs pollution (Deng et al., 2021; Meera et al., 2021; Duan et al., 2021) whereas H. Wu et al., (2023) suggested using the MPs trapping phenomena as a suitability for establishing an aquaculture system inside the mangrove forests to use them as a 'bio-shield' against MPs pollution occurrences. However, the diversity of aquaculture practices in terms of their location makes it limited to some particular aquaculture systems that are situated in the mangrove areas.

5.4. International and regional policies and regulations

Plastic pollution has already gained the attention of international and regional organizations. Recently, 200 nations agreed on a convention to stem the flow of plastic into the ocean. (Smieja, 2022). In the United Nations Environment Assembly (UNEA 5.2) meeting held in Nairobi, Kenya, a committee was formed named the Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee (INC) to stop plastic pollution globally (UNEP, 2022). The main focus of the committee was to include the full life cycle of plastics from production to disposal while establishing criteria to be fulfilled by the different countries when implementing their National Action Plans. Besides, different policies have been made by different regional organizations. The European Union (EU) adopted a plastics strategy in 2018 where microplastics pollution was discussed specifically due to their ubiquity in the environment and foods (European Commission, 2022). Back in 2021, The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN)

decided to adopt a plan of action regionally to reduce marine plastics loads, as six out of 10 members were contributing to around 31 million metric tonnes of plastic waste globally every year (SEADS, 2021). They launched a plan named "ASEAN Regional Action Plan for Combating Marine Debris in the ASEAN Member States (2021–2025)". 1931 was the first year when plastic pollution was observed, although MPs particles were found in marine organisms in the 1990s (Greenwood, 2021). The responses in recent years from the global parties can be considered as late responses." Although different studies suggest making effective regulations in different countries to control the outburst of the MPs pollution, The UN Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee is being considered the 'next big thing' for plastic pollution control in the world. The editorial article from Nature, (2023) has emphasized the role of researchers in the INC's policy design, compliance, and monitoring. So far, no actions have been taken globally except for different regional steps such as introducing biodegradable plastics, investing in research and innovations, training programs, limiting the usage of plastic bags, recycling plastic waste, etc.

6. Conclusion

World's shellfish aquaculture industries have a higher contribution to the annual consumption of shellfish which is expected to be increased in the coming years as wild stocks are not enough to satisfy the demands. The recent shellfish farming trends are indicating that they will lead the shellfish food industries. The ubiquitous emerging pollutant MPs have started to disturb the shellfish culture environment which raises the issue of shellfish production growth, and food security issues. Studies on various aquaculture practices and organisms have shown that MPs are interfering with the shellfish culture system by reducing survival rate, growth, bioaccumulation of toxic substances, and food chain transfers. Before this study, it was unrelated to speculate that, MPs and the shellfish farming operational challenges are strongly interconnected. But this study makes it clearer that, MPs are responsible for the problems faced during culture. So, it is necessary to control the MPs pollution of the culture system. Control measures can be taken by limiting the usage of different plastics equipment in culture practices, removing the plastics particles from the stock water before use, and adopting alternative plastics products in the system. If it cannot be controlled now, the future of the sustainable shellfish aquaculture will be uncertain. More research for the detection of microplastics in the shellfish aquaculture system, their impacts on them, trophic transfers, and human health impact needs to be carried out around the world as the available studies conducted till now do not represent the actual scenario of this farming industry. The plastics usage regulations in aquaculture products from the production to the consumer level should be established before it is too late.

Data Availability

The data used or analyzed during the study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Acknowledgement:

This project was funded by the Ministry of Higher Education, Malaysia through the Fundamental Research Grant Scheme (FRGS) FRGS/1/2020/STG01/UMT/02/4 (vot. No: 59631). The authors would also like to thank the Ministry of Higher Education, Malaysia under the Higher Institution Centre of Excellence (HICoE), Institute of Tropical Aquaculture and Fisheries (AKUATROP) program (Vot. No. 63933 & Vot. No. 56050, UMT/CRIM/2–2/5 Jilid 2 (9)) for supporting this project. The authors appreciate the Institute of Tropical Aquaculture and Fisheries (AKUATROP), Universiti Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia which provides facilities for this research.

Ethics Statement

The authors confirm that the ethical policies of the journal, as noted on the journal's author guidelines page, have been adhered to. The manuscript and the research work were conducted by following all ethical issues given in the journal

Conflicts of interest

The author declares no conflict of interest with the authors and all the guidelines were fully followed and applied.

Author Contributions

Shahadat Hossain: write the full manuscript and conducted the research work, **Zuhayra Nasrin Ahmad Shukri:** assist with writing the manuscript, **Benedict Terkula Iber :** assist with the manuscript conceptualization, **Norhafiza Ilyana Yatim:** assist with the literature review of the manuscript, **Hidayah Manan:** assist with the literature review of the manuscript, **Turabur Rahman:** assist on the preparation of map, **Zahidul Islam:** assist on the manuscript writing and referencing, **Tashrif Mahmud Minhaz:** assist on the manuscript writing, **Helena Khatoon:** assist on the revision of the manuscript, **Khor Waiho:** assist with formatting the manuscript, **Nor Azman Kasan:** project leader and also assist on the final revision.

References

- Abelouah, M. R., Romdhani, I., Ben-Haddad, M., Hajji, S., De-la-Torre, G. E., Gaaied, S., Barra, I., Banni, M., & Alla, A. A. (2023). Binational survey using *Mytilus galloprovincialis* as a bioindicator of microplastic pollution: Insights into chemical analysis and potential risk on humans. *Science of The Total Environment*, 870 (December 2022), 161894. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.161894>
- Abihssira-García, I. S., Kögel, T., Gomiero, A., Kristensen, T., Krogstad, M., & Olsvik, P. A. (2022). Distinct polymer-dependent sorption of persistent pollutants associated with Atlantic salmon farming to microplastics. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 180 (January). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2022.113794>
- Abuwatfa, W. H., Al-Muqbel, D., Al-Othman, A., Halalsheh, N., & Tawalbeh, M. (2021). Insights into the removal of microplastics from water using biochar in the era of COVID-19: A mini review. *Case Studies in Chemical and Environmental Engineering*, 4, 100151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscee.2021.100151>
- Adkisson, K. (2020). *The Root of Microplastics in Plants* | PNNL. Pacific Northwest National Laboratory. <https://www.pnnl.gov/news-media/root-microplastics-plants>
- Ahmadi, A., Moore, F., Keshavarzi, B., Soltani, N., & Sorooshian, A. (2022). Potentially toxic elements and microplastics in muscle tissues of different marine species from the Persian Gulf: Levels, associated risks, and trophic transfer. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 175(January), 113283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2021.113283>
- Akarsu, C., & Deniz, F. (2020). Electrocoagulation / electroflotation process for removal of organics and microplastics in laundry wastewater. *Www.Proteomics-Journal*, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1002/clen.202000146>.This
- Akarsu, C., Kumbur, H., & Kideys, A. E. (2021). Removal of microplastics from wastewater through electrocoagulation-electroflotation and membrane filtration processes. *Water Science and Technology*, 84(7), 1648–1662. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2021.356>
- Amato-Lourenço, L. F., Carvalho-Oliveira, R., Júnior, G. R., dos Santos Galvão, L., Ando, R. A., & Mauad, T. (2021). Presence of airborne microplastics in human lung tissue. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 416(April). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.126124>
- Auta, H. S., Abioye, O. P., Aransiola, S. A., Bala, J. D., Chukwuemeka, V. I., Hassan, A., Aziz, A., & Fauziah,

- S. H. (2022). Enhanced microbial degradation of PET and PS microplastics under natural conditions in mangrove environment. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 304. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JENVMAN.2021.114273>
- Avio, C. G., Gorbi, S., Milan, M., Benedetti, M., Fattorini, D., D'Errico, G., Pauletto, M., Bargelloni, L., & Regoli, F. (2015). Pollutants bioavailability and toxicological risk from microplastics to marine mussels. *Environmental Pollution*, 198, 211–222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2014.12.021>
- Beninger, P. G., & Le Pennec, M. (2016). Scallop Structure and Function. In *Developments in Aquaculture and Fisheries Science* (Vol. 40, Issue 1892). Elsevier B.V. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-62710-0.00003-1>
- Bermúdez, J. R., & Swarzenski, P. W. (2021). A microplastic size classification scheme aligned with universal plankton survey methods. *MethodsX*, 8, 10–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mex.2021.101516>
- Bhuvaneshwari, M., Thiagarajan, V., Nemade, P., Chandrasekaran, N., & Mukherjee, A. (2018). Toxicity and trophic transfer of P25 TiO₂ NPs from *Dunaliella salina* to *Artemia salina*: Effect of dietary and waterborne exposure. *Environmental Research*, 160, 39–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVRES.2017.09.022>
- Bonham, V., Shields, J., & Riginos, C. (2022). *Mytilus galloprovincialis* (Mediterranean mussel). *CABI Compendium*, *CABI Compend.* <https://doi.org/10.1079/CABICOMPENDIUM.73756>
- Brandon, A. M., Gao, S. H., Tian, R., Ning, D., Yang, S. S., Zhou, J., Wu, W. M., & Criddle, C. S. (2018). Biodegradation of Polyethylene and Plastic Mixtures in Mealworms (Larvae of *Tenebrio molitor*) and Effects on the Gut Microbiome. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 52(11), 6526–6533. https://doi.org/10.1021/ACS.EST.8B02301/SUPPL_FILE/ES8B02301_SI_001.PDF
- Brierley, A. S. (2017). Plankton. In *Current Biology* (Vol. 27, Issue 11). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2017.02.045>
- Bringer, A., Thomas, H., Dubillot, E., Le Floch, S., Receveur, J., Cachot, J., & Tran, D. (2021). Subchronic exposure to high-density polyethylene microplastics alone or in combination with chlortoluron significantly affected valve activity and daily growth of the Pacific oyster, *Crassostrea gigas*. *Aquatic Toxicology*, 237(March). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquatox.2021.105880>
- Capanni, F., Greco, S., Tomasi, N., Giulianini, P. G., & Manfrin, C. (2021). Orally administered nano-polystyrene caused vitellogenin alteration and oxidative stress in the red swamp crayfish (*Procambarus clarkii*). *Science*

of the Total Environment, 791, 147984. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.147984>

- Capolupo, M., Franzellitti, S., Valbonesi, P., Lanzas, C. S., & Fabbri, E. (2018). Uptake and transcriptional effects of polystyrene microplastics in larval stages of the Mediterranean mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. *Environmental Pollution*, 241, 1038–1047. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2018.06.035>
- Cappello, T., De Marco, G., Oliveri Conti, G., Giannetto, A., Ferrante, M., Mauceri, A., & Maisano, M. (2021). Time-dependent metabolic disorders induced by short-term exposure to polystyrene microplastics in the Mediterranean mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2020.111780>
- Chazovachii, P. T., Rieland, J. M., Sheffey, V. V., Jugovic, T. M. E., Zimmerman, P. M., Eniola-Adefeso, O., Love, B. J., & McNeil, A. J. (2021). Using Adhesives to Capture Microplastics from Water. *ACS ES&T Engineering*, 1(12), 1698–1704. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ACSESTENGG.1C00272>
- Chen, B., Fan, Y., Huang, W., Rayhan, A. B. M. S., Chen, K., & Cai, M. (2020). Observation of microplastics in mariculture water of Longjiao Bay, southeast China: Influence by human activities. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 160(August), 111655. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2020.111655>
- Chen, Q., Lv, W., Jiao, Y., Liu, Z., Li, Y., Cai, M., Wu, D., Zhou, W., & Zhao, Y. (2020). Effects of exposure to waterborne polystyrene microspheres on lipid metabolism in the hepatopancreas of juvenile redclaw crayfish, *Cherax quadricarinatus*. *Aquatic Toxicology (Amsterdam, Netherlands)*, 224(January), 105497. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquatox.2020.105497>
- Cheng, Y. R., & Wang, H. Y. (2022). Highly effective removal of microplastics by microalgae *Scenedesmus abundans*. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 435(P2), 135079. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.135079>
- Choi, J. S., Kim, K., Park, K., & Park, J. W. (2022). Long-term exposure of the Mediterranean mussels, *Mytilus galloprovincialis* to polyethylene terephthalate microfibers: Implication for reproductive and neurotoxic effects. *Chemosphere*, 299(March). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.134317>
- Cholewińska, P., Moniuszko, H., Wojnarowski, K., Pokorny, P., Szeligowska, N., Dobicki, W., Polechoński, R., & Górniak, W. (2022). The Occurrence of Microplastics and the Formation of Biofilms by Pathogenic and Opportunistic Bacteria as Threats in Aquaculture. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(13). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19138137>

- Commission of the European Communities. (2006). Commission Regulation (EC) No 118/2006 of 19 December 2006 setting maximum levels for certain contaminants in foodstuffs. *Official Journal of the European Union*, 364, 5–24.
- Corami, F., Rosso, B., Roman, M., Picone, M., Gambaro, A., & Barbante, C. (2020). Evidence of small microplastics (<100 µm) ingestion by Pacific oysters (*Crassostrea gigas*): A novel method of extraction, purification, and analysis using Micro-FTIR. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 160(August), 111606. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2020.111606>
- Cunningham, E. M., & Sigwart, J. D. (2019). Environmentally accurate microplastic levels and their absence from exposure studies. *Integrative and Comparative Biology*, 59(6), 1485–1496. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icb/icz068>
- Danopoulos, E., Twiddy, M., West, R., & Rotchell, J. M. (2022). A rapid review and meta-regression analyses of the toxicological impacts of microplastic exposure in human cells. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 427(September 2021), 127861. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.127861>
- de Wilt, A., Butkovskiy, A., Tuantet, K., Leal, L. H., Fernandes, T. V., Langenhoff, A., & Zeeman, G. (2016). Micropollutant removal in an algal treatment system fed with source separated wastewater streams. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 304, 84–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2015.10.033>
- Deng, H., He, J., Feng, D., Zhao, Y., Sun, W., Yu, H., & Ge, C. (2021). Microplastics pollution in mangrove ecosystems: A critical review of current knowledge and future directions. *Science of the Total Environment*, 753, 142041. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.142041>
- Do, V. M., Dang, T. T., Le, X. T. T., Nguyen, D. T., Phung, T. V., Vu, D. N., & Pham, H. V. (2022). Abundance of microplastics in cultured oysters (*Crassostrea gigas*) from Danang Bay of Vietnam. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 180(January), 113800. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2022.113800>
- Dong, H., Chen, Y., Wang, J., Zhang, Y., Zhang, P., Li, X., Zou, J., & Zhou, A. (2021). Interactions of microplastics and antibiotic resistance genes and their effects on the aquaculture environments. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 403(July 2020), 123961. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2020.123961>
- Du, Y., Zhao, J., Teng, J., Ren, J., Zheng, P., Zhu, X., Liu, Y., Sun, X., Yuan, S., & Wang, Q. (2022). Seasonal change of microplastics uptake in the Pacific oysters *Crassostrea gigas* cultured in the Yellow Sea and Bohai

- Sea, China. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 185(PB), 114341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2022.114341>
- Duan, J., Han, J., Cheung, S. G., Chong, R. K. Y., Lo, C. M., Lee, F. W. F., Xu, S. J. L., Yang, Y., Tam, N. F. yee, & Zhou, H. C. (2021). How mangrove plants affect microplastic distribution in sediments of coastal wetlands: Case study in Shenzhen Bay, South China. *Science of the Total Environment*, 767, 144695. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144695>
- Elmahdi, S., DaSilva, L. V., & Parveen, S. (2016). Antibiotic resistance of *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* and *Vibrio vulnificus* in various countries: A review. *Food Microbiology*, 57, 128–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2016.02.008>
- Emenike, E. C., Iwuzor, K. O., & Anidiobi, S. U. (2022). Heavy Metal Pollution in Aquaculture: Sources, Impacts and Mitigation Techniques. *Biological Trace Element Research*, 200(10), 4476–4492. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12011-021-03037-x>
- European Commission. (2022). *Plastics*. European Commission; Energy, Climate Change, Environment. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/plastics_en
- FAO. (2018). *SOFIA 2018 | FAO | Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations*. <https://www.fao.org/publications/sofia/2018/en/>
- FAO. (2020). Food balance sheets on apparent consumption | Coordinating Working Party on Fishery Statistics (CWP) | *Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations*. <https://www.fao.org/cwp-on-fishery-statistics/handbook/socio-economic-dimension/food-balance-sheets/en/>
- FAO. (2022). World Fisheries and Aquaculture, *FAO:Rome,2022*. https://www.fao.org/3/ca9229en/online/ca9229en.html#chapter-1_1
- Fernández, B., Campillo, J. A., Chaves-Pozo, E., Bellas, J., León, V. M., & Albentosa, M. (2022). Comparative role of microplastics and microalgae as vectors for chlorpyrifos bioaccumulation and related physiological and immune effects in mussels. *Science of the Total Environment*, 807. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.150983>
- Frias, J. P. G. L., & Nash, R. (2019). Microplastics: Finding a consensus on the definition. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 138, 145–147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MARPOLBUL.2018.11.022>

- Fu, L., Li, J., Wang, G., Luan, Y., & Dai, W. (2021). Adsorption behavior of organic pollutants on microplastics. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 217(April), 112207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2021.112207>
- Gardner, C., Watson, R. A., Jayanti, A. D., Suadi, AlHusaini, M., & Kruse, G. H. (2021). Crustaceans as fisheries resources: General overview. *Fisheries and Aquaculture: Volume 9*, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780190865627.003.0001>
- Garr, A. L., Lopez, H., Pierce, R., & Davis, M. (2011). The effect of stocking density and diet on the growth and survival of cultured Florida apple snails, *Pomacea paludosa*. *Aquaculture*, 311(1–4), 139–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2010.11.017>
- Gasperi, J., Wright, S. L., Dris, R., Collard, F., Mandin, C., Guerrouache, M., Langlois, V., Kelly, F. J., & Tassin, B. (2018). Microplastics in air: Are we breathing it in? *Current Opinion in Environmental Science and Health*, 1, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coesh.2017.10.002>
- Gholamhosseini, A., Banaee, M., Sureda, A., Timar, N., Zeidi, A., & Faggio, C. (2023). Physiological response of freshwater crayfish, *Astacus leptodactylus* exposed to polyethylene microplastics at different temperature. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part - C: Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 267(September 2022), 109581. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpc.2023.109581>
- Gill, M. (2014). Bioplastic: a Better Alternative To Plastics. *Impact Journals*, 2(8), 115–120. <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.684.9671&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- González-Soto, N., Campos, L., Navarro, E., Bilbao, E., Guilhermino, L., & Cajaraville, M. P. (2022). Effects of microplastics alone or with sorbed oil compounds from the water accommodated fraction of a North Sea crude oil on marine mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*). *Science of the Total Environment*, 851(May). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.157999>
- Graham, P., Palazzo, L., Andrea de Lucia, G., Telfer, T. C., Baroli, M., & Carboni, S. (2019). Microplastics uptake and egestion dynamics in Pacific oysters, *Magallana gigas* (Thunberg, 1793), under controlled conditions. *Environmental Pollution*, 252, 742–748. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2019.06.002>
- Green, D. S., Boots, B., Sigwart, J., Jiang, S., & Rocha, C. (2016). Effects of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on a marine ecosystem engineer (*Arenicola marina*) and sediment nutrient cycling.

Environmental Pollution, 208, 426–434. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2015.10.010>

Green, D. S., Colgan, T. J., Thompson, R. C., & Carolan, J. C. (2019). Exposure to microplastics reduces attachment strength and alters the haemolymph proteome of blue mussels (*Mytilus edulis*). *Environmental Pollution*, 246, 423–434. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2018.12.017>

Greenwood, K. (2021). *History of Plastic Production*. Plastic Collective. <https://www.plasticcollective.co/history-of-plastic-production/>

Guo, Y. M., Huang, Z. L., Guo, J., Li, H., Guo, X. R., & Nkeli, M. J. (2019). Bibliometric analysis on smart cities research. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(13). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11133606>

Han, Y., Shi, W., Tang, Y., Zhou, W., Sun, H., Zhang, J., Yan, M., Hu, L., & Liu, G. (2022). Microplastics and bisphenol A hamper gonadal development of whiteleg shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) by interfering with metabolism and disrupting hormone regulation. *Science of the Total Environment*, 810, 152354. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.152354>

Han, Y., Zhou, W., Tang, Y., Shi, W., Shao, Y., Ren, P., Zhang, J., Xiao, G., Sun, H., & Liu, G. (2021). Microplastics aggravate the bioaccumulation of three veterinary antibiotics in the thick shell mussel *Mytilus coruscus* and induce synergistic immunotoxic effects. *Science of the Total Environment*, 770, 145273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.145273>

Hange, K., & Awofolu, O. R. (2017). Assessment of anthropogenic influence on the level of selected heavy metals (Cu, Zn, Cd and Pb) in soil. *Journal of Soil Science and Environmental Management* 8(6), 113–121. <https://doi.org/10.5897/JSSEM2017.0630>

Harmon, S. M. (2015). The Toxicity of Persistent Organic Pollutants to Aquatic Organisms. In *Comprehensive Analytical Chemistry* (Vol. 67). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-63299-9.00018-1>

Hartmann, N. B., Rist, S., Bodin, J., Jensen, L. H. S., Schmidt, S. N., Mayer, P., Meibom, A., & Baun, A. (2017). Microplastics as vectors for environmental contaminants: Exploring sorption, desorption, and transfer to biota. *Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management*, 13(3), 488–493. <https://doi.org/10.1002/IEAM.1904>

He, Y., Caporaso, J. G., Jiang, X.-T., Sheng, H.-F., Huse, S. M., Rideout, J. R., Edgar, R. C., Kopylova, E., Walters, W. A., Knight, R., & Zhou, H.-W. (2015). Stability of operational taxonomic units: an important

- but neglected property for analyzing microbial diversity. *Microbiome*, 3(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40168-015-0081-x>
- Hernández-López, M., & Romero, D. (2022). Chronic Microplastic Exposure and Cadmium Accumulation in Blue Crabs. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19095631>
- Hidayati, N. V., Asia, L., Khabouchi, I., Torre, F., Widowati, I., Sabdon, A., Doumenq, P., & Syakti, A. D. (2021). Ecological risk assessment of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in surface sediments from aquaculture system. *Chemosphere*, 263, 128372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.128372>
- Holt, C. C., Bass, D., Stentiford, G. D., & van der Giezen, M. (2021). Understanding the role of the shrimp gut microbiome in health and disease. *Journal of Invertebrate Pathology*, 186(September 2019), 107387. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jip.2020.107387>
- Horn, D. A., Granek, E. F., & Steele, C. L. (2020). Effects of environmentally relevant concentrations of microplastic fibers on Pacific mole crab (*Emerita analoga*) mortality and reproduction. *Limnology And Oceanography Letters*, 5(1), 74–83. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lol2.10137>
- Horstman, E. M., Dohmen-Janssen, C. M., Bouma, T. J., & Hulscher, S. J. M. H. (2015). Tidal-scale flow routing and sedimentation in mangrove forests: Combining field data and numerical modelling. *Geomorphology*, 228, 244–262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2014.08.011>
- Hossain, S., Ahmad Shukri, Z. N., Waiho, K., Ibrahim, Y. S., Minhaz, T. M., Kamaruzzan, A. S., Abdul Rahim, A. I., Draman, A. S., Khatoon, H., Islam, Z., & Kasan, N. A. (2023). Microplastics pollution in mud crab (*Scylla* sp.) aquaculture system: First investigation and evidence. *Environmental Pollution*, 329(April), 121697. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2023.121697>
- Hossain, S., Manan, H., Shukri, Z. N. A., Othman, R., Kamaruzzan, A. S., Rahim, A. I. A., Khatoon, H., Minhaz, T. M., Islam, Z., & Kasan, N. A. (2023a). Microplastics biodegradation by biofloc-producing bacteria: An inventive biofloc technology approach. *Microbiological Research*, 266(October 2022), 127239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micres.2022.127239>
- Hu, L., Zhao, Y., & Xu, H. (2022). Trojan horse in the intestine: A review on the biotoxicity of microplastics combined environmental contaminants. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 439(July), 129652.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.129652>

- Huang, S., Huang, X., Bi, R., Guo, Q., Yu, X., Zeng, Q., Huang, Z., Liu, T., Wu, H., Chen, Y., Xu, J., Wu, Y., & Guo, P. (2022). Detection and Analysis of Microplastics in Human Sputum. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 56(4), 2476–2486. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c03859>
- Hue, H. T. T., Dong, L. K., Hien, T. T., Nguyen, T. N., & Pradit, S. (2021). Assessment of microplastics contamination in commercial clams in the coastal zone of Vietnam. *Applied Ecology and Environmental Research*, 19(6), 4977–4991. https://doi.org/10.15666/aecer/1906_49774991
- Jaikumar, I. M., Periyakali, S. B., Rajendran, U., Joen-Rong, S., Thanasekaran, J., & Tsorng-Harn, F. (2021). Effects of Microplastics, Polystyrene, and Polyethylene on Antioxidants, Metabolic Enzymes, HSP-70, and Myostatin Expressions in the Giant River Prawn *Macrobrachium rosenbergii*: Impact on Survival and Growth. *Archives of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, 80(3), 645–658. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00244-021-00833-3>
- Janaswamy, S., Yadav, M. P., Hoque, M., Bhattarai, S., & Ahmed, S. (2022). Cellulosic fraction from agricultural biomass as a viable alternative for plastics and plastic products. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 179(February), 114692. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2022.114692>
- Jeyavani, J., Sibiya, A., Bhavaniramy, S., Mahboob, S., Al-Ghanim, K. A., Nisa, Z. un, Riaz, M. N., Nicoletti, M., Govindarajan, M., & Vaseeharan, B. (2022). Toxicity evaluation of polypropylene microplastic on marine microcrustacean *Artemia salina*: An analysis of implications and vulnerability. *Chemosphere*, 296(January), 133990. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.133990>
- Jeyavani, J., & Vaseeharan, B. (2023). Combined toxic effects of environmental predominant microplastics and ZnO nanoparticles in freshwater snail *Pomacea paludosa*. *Environmental Pollution*, 325(January), 121427. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2023.121427>
- Jiang, W., Fang, J., Du, M., Gao, Y., Fang, J., & Jiang, Z. (2022). Microplastics influence physiological processes, growth and reproduction in the Manila clam, *Ruditapes philippinarum*. *Environmental Pollution*, 293(September 2021), 118502. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.118502>
- K.V., J., Ebeneazar, S., P., S., V. Nair, A., & P., K. (2021). Dietary supplementation of microalgae, *Aurantiochytrium* sp. and co-feeding with *Artemia* enhances the growth, stress tolerance and survival in

- Penaeus monodon (Fabricius, 1798) post larvae. *Aquaculture*, 533(October 2020), 736176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.736176>
- Kandathil Radhakrishnan, D., AkbarAli, I., Schmidt, B. V., John, E. M., Sivanpillai, S., & Thazhakot Vasunambesan, S. (2020). Improvement of nutritional quality of live feed for aquaculture: An overview. *Aquaculture Research*, 51(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ARE.14357>
- Kibenge, F. S. B. (2022). Descriptions of major farmed aquatic animal species. In *Aquaculture Pathophysiology: Finfish Diseases: Volume I* (Vol. 1). Elsevier Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-812211-2.00041-X>
- Klein, K., Heß, S., Nungeß, S., Schulte-Oehlmann, U., & Oehlmann, J. (2021). Particle shape does not affect ingestion and egestion of microplastics by the freshwater shrimp *Neocaridina palmata*. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(44), 62246–62254. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-15068-x>
- Kokalj, A. J., Kunej, U., & Skalar, T. (2018). Screening study of four environmentally relevant microplastic pollutants: Uptake and effects on *Daphnia magna* and *Artemia franciscana*. *Chemosphere*, 208, 522–529. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.05.172>
- Kuruppallil, Z. (2011). Green Plastics: An Emerging Alternative for Petroleum-Based Plastics. *International Journal of Engineering Research & Innovation*, 3(1), 59–64. <http://ijeri.org/IJERI-Archives/issues/spring2011/IJERIVol3N1Spring2011final1.PDF#page=61>
- Lan, R., Wei, Y., & Xue, R. (2021). Uptake of polystyrene microplastics by marine rotifers under different experimental conditions. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 687(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/687/1/012071>
- Lee, J., Wang, J., Oh, Y., & Jeong, S. (2023). Highly efficient microplastics removal from water using in-situ ferrate coagulation: Performance evaluation by micro-Fourier-transformed infrared spectroscopy and coagulation mechanism. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 451(P2), 138556. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.138556>
- LGA, B., A, D. V., BRBO, L., AK, L., & L, G. (2018). Marine microplastic debris: An emerging issue for food security, food safety and human health. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 133, 336–348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MARPOLBUL.2018.05.047>
- Li, L. L., Amara, R., Souissi, S., Dehaut, A., Duflos, G., & Monchy, S. (2020). Impacts of microplastics exposure

- on mussel (*Mytilus edulis*) gut microbiota. *Science of the Total Environment*, 745. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141018>
- Li, Z., Junaid, M., Chen, G., & Wang, J. (2022). Interactions and associated resistance development mechanisms between microplastics, antibiotics and heavy metals in the aquaculture environment. *Reviews in Aquaculture*, 14(2), 1028–1045. <https://doi.org/10.1111/raq.12639>
- Liu, C., Luan, P., Li, Q., Cheng, Z., Sun, X., Cao, D., & Zhu, H. (2020). Biodegradable, Hygienic, and Compostable Tableware from Hybrid Sugarcane and Bamboo Fibers as Plastic Alternative. *Matter*, 3(6), 2066–2079. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matt.2020.10.004>
- Liu, F., Nord, N. B., Bester, K., & Vollertsen, J. (2020). Microplastics removal from treated wastewater by a biofilter. *Water (Switzerland)*, 12(4), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/W12041085>
- Liu, X., Liu, H., Chen, L., & Wang, X. (2022). Ecological interception effect of mangroves on microplastics. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 423(PB), 127231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.127231>
- Liu, X., Yuan, W., Di, M., Li, Z., & Wang, J. (2019). Transfer and fate of microplastics during the conventional activated sludge process in one wastewater treatment plant of China. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 362(January), 176–182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2019.01.033>
- Liu, Y., Liu, W., Yang, X., Wang, J., Lin, H., & Yang, Y. (2021). Microplastics are a hotspot for antibiotic resistance genes: Progress and perspective. *Science of the Total Environment*, 773(1), 145643. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.145643>
- Liu, Z., Yu, P., Cai, M., Wu, D., Zhang, M., Chen, M., & Zhao, Y. (2019). Effects of microplastics on the innate immunity and intestinal microflora of juvenile *Eriocheir sinensis*. *Science of the Total Environment*, 685, 836–846. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.06.265>
- Lopes, L. G. A., Lopes, F. C., Quintana, K. G., Costa, P. G., de Martinez Gaspar Martins, C., & Souza, M. M. (2023). Biomineralization biomarkers to assess microplastics toxic effects in the freshwater snail *Pomacea canaliculata*. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part - C: Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 268(October 2022), 109585. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpc.2023.109585>
- Louzán A, Nóvoa S, Ojea J, Da Costa F, M.-P. D. (2016). *Culture of the wedge-shell clam Donax trunculus: new developments.* Nova Science Publishers.

[https://www.researchgate.net/publication/308363738_Culture_of_the_wedge
shell_clam_Donax_trunculus_new_developments](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/308363738_Culture_of_the_wedge_shell_clam_Donax_trunculus_new_developments)

- Lu, J., Zhang, Y., Wu, J., & Luo, Y. (2019). Effects of microplastics on distribution of antibiotic resistance genes in recirculating aquaculture system. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 184(September), 109631. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2019.109631>
- Luan, L., Wang, X., Zheng, H., Liu, L., Luo, X., & Li, F. (2019). Differential toxicity of functionalized polystyrene microplastics to clams (*Meretrix meretrix*) at three key development stages of life history. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 139(November 2018), 346–354. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2019.01.003>
- Luo, Y. Y., Not, C., & Cannicci, S. (2021). Mangroves as unique but understudied traps for anthropogenic marine debris: A review of present information and the way forward. *Environmental Pollution*, 271, 116291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.116291>
- Magara, G., Elia, A. C., Syberg, K., & Khan, F. R. (2018). Single contaminant and combined exposures of polyethylene microplastics and fluoranthene: accumulation and oxidative stress response in the blue mussel, *Mytilus edulis*. *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health - Part A: Current Issues*, 81(16), 761–773. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15287394.2018.1488639>
- Magara, G., Khan, F. R., Pinti, M., Syberg, K., Inzirillo, A., & Elia, A. C. (2019). Effects of combined exposures of fluoranthene and polyethylene or polyhydroxybutyrate microplastics on oxidative stress biomarkers in the blue mussel (*Mytilus edulis*). *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health - Part A: Current Issues*, 82(10), 616–625. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15287394.2019.1633451>
- Martelli, A., Barbieri, E. S., Dima, J. B., & Barón, P. J. (2020). Rearing enhancement of *Ovalipes trimaculatus* (Crustacea: Portunidae) zoea I by feeding on *Artemia persimilis* nauplii enriched with alternative microalgal diets. *Scientific Reports 2020 10:1*, 10(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-67933-3>
- McDaid, A., Cunningham, E. M., Crump, A., Hardiman, G., & Arnott, G. (2023). Does microplastic exposure and sex influence shell selection and motivation in the common European hermit crab, *Pagurus bernhardus*? *Science of the Total Environment*, 855(September 2022), 158576. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.158576>
- Meera, S. P., Bhattacharyya, M., Nizam, A., & Kumar, A. (2021). A review on microplastic pollution in the

- mangrove wetlands and microbial strategies for its remediation. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 2021 29:4, 29(4), 4865–4879. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11356-021-17451-0>
- Munier, B., & Bendell, L. I. (2018). Macro and micro plastics sorb and desorb metals and act as a point source of trace metals to coastal ecosystems. *PLoS ONE*, 13(2), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0191759>
- Munuera, P., Salvat-Leal, I., Belmonte, A., & Romero, D. (2021). Can microplastics influence the accumulation of pb in tissues of blue crab? *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18073599>
- Murphy, K. (Kenneth M. ., Weaver, C., Berg, L., Barton, G., & Janeway, C. A. (2022). *Janeway's immunobiology*.
- Murray, F., & Cowie, P. R. (2011). Plastic contamination in the decapod crustacean *Nephrops norvegicus* (Linnaeus, 1758). *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 62(6), 1207–1217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MARPOLBUL.2011.03.032>
- Nature. (2023). Plastic waste is everywhere —countries must be held accountable. *Nature*, 619(7969), 221. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-023-02251-y>
- Network Of Aquaculture Centres In Asia. (1988). Status of mollusc culture in selected Asian countries. <https://www.fao.org/3/ab718e/AB718E00.htm#TOC>
- Nobre, C. R., Moreno, B. B., Alves, A. V., de Lima Rosa, J., Fontes, M. K., Campos, B. G. de, Silva, L. F. da, Almeida Duarte, L. F. de, Abessa, D. M. de S., Choueri, R. B., Gusso-Choueri, P. K., & Pereira, C. D. S. (2022). Combined effects of polyethylene spiked with the antimicrobial triclosan on the swamp ghost crab (*Ucides cordatus*; Linnaeus, 1763). *Chemosphere*, 304(January). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.135169>
- Nugrahapraja, H., Sugiyo, P. W. W., Putri, B. Q., Ni'matuzahroh, Fatimah, Huang, L., Hafza, N., Götz, F., Santoso, H., Wibowo, A. T., & Luqman, A. (2022). Effects of Microplastic on Human Gut Microbiome: Detection of Plastic-Degrading Genes in Human Gut Exposed to Microplastics—Preliminary Study. *Environments - MDPI*, 9(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments9110140>
- O'Donovan, S., Mestre, N. C., Abel, S., Fonseca, T. G., Carteny, C. C., Cormier, B., Keiter, S. H., & Bebianno, M. J. (2018). Ecotoxicological effects of chemical contaminants adsorbed to microplastics in the Clam *Scrobicularia plana*. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 5(APR). <https://doi.org/10.3389/FMARS.2018.00143>

- O'Donovan, S., Mestre, N. C., Abel, S., Fonseca, T. G., Carteny, C. C., Willems, T., Prinsen, E., Cormier, B., Keiter, S. S., & Bebianno, M. J. (2020). Effects of the UV filter, oxybenzone, adsorbed to microplastics in the clam *Scrobicularia plana*. *Science of the Total Environment*, 733, 139102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.139102>
- Ouyang, X., & Guo, F. (2016). Paradigms of mangroves in treatment of anthropogenic wastewater pollution. *Science of the Total Environment*, 544, 971–979. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.12.013>
- Park, B. H., Park, M. S., Kim, B. Y., Hur, S. B., & Kim, S. J. (1988). *Culture of the Pacific Oyster (Crassostrea gigas) in the Republic of Korea*. <https://www.fao.org/3/AB706E/AB706E05.htm>
- Park, J., Kim, P. K., & Jo, J. Y. (2008). Growth performance of disk abalone *Haliotis discus hannai* in pilot- and commercial-scale recirculating aquaculture systems. *Aquaculture International*, 16(3), 191–202. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10499-007-9136-8>
- Parker, L. (2021). *Plastic gets to the oceans through over 1,000 rivers*. <https://www.nationalgeographic.com/environment/article/plastic-gets-to-oceans-through-over-1000-rivers>
- Parra, S., Varandas, S., Santos, D., Fernandes, L., Cabecinha, E., & Monteiro, S. M. (2021). Multi-Biomarker Responses of Asian Clam *Corbicula fluminea*.
- Programme, U.-U. E. (2022). Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee (INC) on Plastic Pollution. <https://www.unep.org/about-un-environment/inc-plastic-pollution>
- Qin, M., Chen, C., Song, B., Shen, M., Cao, W., Yang, H., Zeng, G., & Gong, J. (2021). A review of biodegradable plastics to biodegradable microplastics: Another ecological threat to soil environments? *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 312(February), 127816. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127816>
- Reunura, T., & Prommi, T. O. (2022). Detection of microplastics in *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Penaeidae) and *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* (Palaemonidae) in cultured pond. *PeerJ*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.12916>
- Ribeiro, F., Garcia, A. R., Pereira, B. P., Fonseca, M., Mestre, N. C., Fonseca, T. G., Ilharco, L. M., & Bebianno, M. J. (2017). Microplastics effects in *Scrobicularia plana*. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 122(1–2), 379–391. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2017.06.078>

- Rodríguez-Narvaez, O. M., Goonetilleke, A., Perez, L., & Bandala, E. R. (2021). Engineered technologies for the separation and degradation of microplastics in water: A review. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 414(January), 128692. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.128692>
- Ruiz, A. (2023). 25 Jaw-Dropping Plastic Waste Statistics in 2023 - The Roundup. <https://theroundup.org/plastic-waste-statistics/>
- Santos, L. H. M. L. M., Rodríguez-Mozaz, S., & Barceló, D. (2021). Microplastics as vectors of pharmaceuticals in aquatic organisms – An overview of their environmental implications. *Case Studies in Chemical and Environmental Engineering*, 3(October 2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscee.2021.100079>
- Sapkota, A., Sapkota, A. R., Kucharski, M., Burke, J., McKenzie, S., Walker, P., & Lawrence, R. (2008). Aquaculture practices and potential human health risks: Current knowledge and future priorities. *Environment International*, 34(8), 1215–1226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2008.04.009>
- SEADS. (2021). *Southeast Asia Takes Action against Plastic Pollution*. Southeast Asia Development Solutions. <https://seads.adb.org/news/southeast-asia-takes-action-against-plastic-pollution>
- Shang, Y., Gu, H., Li, S., Chang, X., Sokolova, I., Fang, J. K. H., Wei, S., Chen, X., Hu, M., Huang, W., & Wang, Y. (2021). Microplastics and food shortage impair the byssal attachment of thick-shelled mussel *Mytilus coruscus*. *Marine Environmental Research*, 171(August). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2021.105455>
- Shen, M., Hu, T., Huang, W., Song, B., Zeng, G., & Zhang, Y. (2021). Removal of microplastics from wastewater with aluminosilicate filter media and their surfactant-modified products: Performance, mechanism and utilization. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 421(P1), 129918. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.129918>
- Shen, M., Zhang, Y., Almatrafi, E., Hu, T., Zhou, C., Song, B., Zeng, Z., & Zeng, G. (2022). Efficient removal of microplastics from wastewater by an electrocoagulation process. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 428(July 2021), 131161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.131161>
- Shi, X., Zhang, X., Gao, W., Zhang, Y., & He, D. (2022). Removal of microplastics from water by magnetic nano-Fe₃O₄. *Science of the Total Environment*, 802, 149838. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.149838>
- Siddiqui, S. A., Bahmid, N. A., Salman, S. H. M., Nawaz, A., Walayat, N., Shekhawat, G. K., Gvozdenko, A. A., Blinov, A. V., & Nagdalian, A. A. (2023). Migration of microplastics from plastic packaging into foods and its potential threats on human health. In *Advances in Food and Nutrition Research* (1st ed., Vol. 103).

Elsevier Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.afnr.2022.07.002>

- Sıkdokur, E., Belivermiş, M., Sezer, N., Pekmez, M., Bulan, Ö. K., & Kılıç, Ö. (2020). Effects of microplastics and mercury on manila clam *Ruditapes philippinarum*: Feeding rate, immunomodulation, histopathology and oxidative stress. *Environmental Pollution*, 262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.114247>
- Smieja, J. (2022). *A new initiative to fight plastic waste is working*. World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2019/09/we-created-an-initiative-to-fight-plastic-waste-here-are-3-takeaways-from-our-first-year/>
- Srisomwong, M., Meksumpun, S., Wangvoralak, S., Thawonsode, N., & Meksumpun, C. (2018). Production potential of tidal flats for blood clam (*Anadara granosa*) culture in Bang-tabun bay, Phetchaburi province. *ScienceAsia*, 44(6), 388–396. <https://doi.org/10.2306/SCIENCEASIA1513-1874.2018.44.388>
- Statista. (2023a). *Fish consumption in the U.S. 2018* | Statista. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/656883/us-consumption-of-fish-and-shellfish/>
- Statista. (2023b). *Plastic production worldwide 2021* | Statista. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/282732/global-production-of-plastics-since-1950/>
- Statista. (2023c). *Seafood: per capita consumption worldwide 2020* | Statista. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/820953/per-capita-consumption-of-seafood-worldwide/#statisticContainer>
- Sturm, M. T., Herbort, A. F., Horn, H., & Schuhen, K. (2020). Comparative study of the influence of linear and branched alkyltrichlorosilanes on the removal efficiency of polyethylene and polypropylene-based microplastic particles from water. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 27(10), 10888–10898. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-07712-9>
- Sturm, M. T., Horn, H., & Schuhen, K. (2021). Removal of microplastics from waters through agglomeration-fixation using organosilanes—effects of polymer types, water composition and temperature. *Water (Switzerland)*, 13(5), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13050675>
- Sui, Y., Zheng, L., Chen, Y., Xue, Z., Cao, Y., Mohsen, M., Nguyen, H., Zhang, S., Lv, L., & Wang, C. (2022). Combined effects of short term exposure to seawater acidification and microplastics on the early development of the oyster *Crassostrea rivularis*. *Aquaculture*, 549(November 2021), 737746.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2021.737746>

- Sun, S., Jin, Y., Luo, P., & Shi, X. (2022). Polystyrene microplastics induced male reproductive toxicity and transgenerational effects in freshwater prawn. *Science of the Total Environment*, 842(June), 156820. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.156820>
- Sutherland, D. L., & Ralph, P. J. (2019). Microalgal bioremediation of emerging contaminants - Opportunities and challenges. *Water Research*, 164, 114921. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2019.114921>
- Ta, A. T., Pupuang, P., Babel, S., & Wang, L. P. (2022). Investigation of microplastic contamination in blood cockles and green mussels from selected aquaculture farms and markets in Thailand. *Chemosphere*, 303(P1), 134918. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.134918>
- Tan, Y., Fang, L., Qiu, M., Huo, Z., & Yan, X. (2020). Population genetics of the Manila in East Asia. *Scientific Reports*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-78923-w>
- Tang, G., Liu, M., Zhou, Q., He, H., Chen, K., Zhang, H., Hu, J., Huang, Q., Luo, Y., Ke, H., Chen, B., Xu, X., & Cai, M. (2018). Microplastics and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in Xiamen coastal areas: Implications for anthropogenic impacts. *Science of the Total Environment*, 634, 811–820. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.03.336>
- Tang, Y., Han, Y., Zhang, W., Yu, Y., Huang, L., Zhou, W., Shi, W., Tian, D., & Liu, G. (2022). Bisphenol A and microplastics weaken the antimicrobial ability of blood clams by disrupting humoral immune responses and suppressing hemocyte chemotactic activity. *Environmental Pollution*, 307(January), 119497. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2022.119497>
- Tang, Y., Zhang, S., Su, Y., Wu, D., Zhao, Y., & Xie, B. (2021). Removal of microplastics from aqueous solutions by magnetic carbon nanotubes. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 406(July 2020), 126804. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2020.126804>
- Teng, J., Wang, Q., Ran, W., Wu, D., Liu, Y., Sun, S., Liu, H., Cao, R., & Zhao, J. (2019). Microplastic in cultured oysters from different coastal areas of China. *Science of the Total Environment*, 653, 1282–1292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.11.057>
- Teng, J., Zhao, J., Zhu, X., Shan, E., Zhang, C., Zhang, W., & Wang, Q. (2021). Toxic effects of exposure to microplastics with environmentally relevant shapes and concentrations: Accumulation, energy metabolism

- and tissue damage in oyster *Crassostrea gigas*. *Environmental Pollution*, 269, 116169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.116169>
- Thakur, B., Singh, J., Singh, J., Angmo, D., & Vig, A. P. (2023). Biodegradation of different types of microplastics: Molecular mechanism and degradation efficiency. *Science of The Total Environment*, 877(March), 162912. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.162912>
- The European market for mussels | GLOBEFISH | *Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations*. Retrieved in 2023, from <https://www.fao.org/in-action/globefish/fishery-information/resource-detail/en/c/338588/>
- Tlili, S., Jemai, D., Brinis, S., & Regaya, I. (2020). Microplastics mixture exposure at environmentally relevant conditions induce oxidative stress and neurotoxicity in the wedge clam *Donax trunculus*. *Chemosphere*, 258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.127344>
- Urbina, M. A., da Silva Montes, C., Schäfer, A., Castillo, N., Urzúa, Á., & Lagos, M. E. (2023). Slow and steady hurts the crab: Effects of chronic and acute microplastic exposures on a filter feeder crab. *Science of the Total Environment*, 857(September 2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.159135>
- Valsan, G., Tamrakar, A., & Warriar, A. K. (2024). Microplastics in *Scylla Serrata* : A baseline study from southwest India. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 200(January), 116109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2024.116109>
- Villegas, L., Cabrera, M., Moulatlet, G. M., & Capparelli, M. (2022). The synergistic effect of microplastic and malathion exposure on fiddler crab *Minuca ecuadoriensis* microplastic bioaccumulation and survival. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 175(January), 113336. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2022.113336>
- von Hellfeld, R., Zarzuelo, M., Zaldibar, B., Cajaraville, M. P., & Orbea, A. (2022). Accumulation, Depuration, and Biological Effects of Polystyrene Microplastic Spheres and Adsorbed Cadmium and Benzo(a)pyrene on the Mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. *Toxics*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics10010018>
- Walkinshaw, C., Lindeque, P. K., Thompson, R., Tolhurst, T., & Cole, M. (2020). Microplastics and seafood: lower trophic organisms at highest risk of contamination. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 190(August 2019), 110066. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2019.110066>
- Wang, C., Yu, J., Lu, Y., Hua, D., Wang, X., & Zou, X. (2021). Biodegradable microplastics (BMPs): a new cause

- for concern? *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(47), 66511–66518.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-16435-4>
- Wang, F., Wu, H., Wu, W., Wang, L., Liu, J., An, L., & Xu, Q. (2021). Microplastic characteristics in organisms of different trophic levels from Liaohe Estuary, China. *Science of the Total Environment*, 789, 148027.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.148027>
- Wang, P., Huang, Z., Chen, S., Jing, M., Ge, Z., Chen, J., Yang, S., Chen, J., & Fang, Y. (2022). Sustainable removal of nano/microplastics in water by solar energy. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 428(July 2021), 131196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.131196>
- Wang, Q., Liu, J., Zhang, S., Lian, Y., Ding, H., Du, X., Li, Z., & De Silva, S. S. (2016). Sustainable farming practices of the Chinese mitten crab (*Eriocheir sinensis*) around Hongze Lake, lower Yangtze River Basin, China. *Ambio*, 45(3), 361–373. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-015-0722-0>
- Wang, T., Hu, M., Xu, G., Shi, H., Leung, J. Y. S., & Wang, Y. (2021). Microplastic accumulation via trophic transfer: Can a predatory crab counter the adverse effects of microplastics by body defence? *Science of the Total Environment*, 754, 142099. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.142099>
- Wang, W., Yang, M., Ma, H., Liu, Z., Gai, L., Zheng, Z., & Ma, H. (2023). Removal behaviors and mechanism of polystyrene microplastics by coagulation / ultra filtration process : Co-effects of humic acid. *Science of the Total Environment*, 881(January), 163408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.163408>
- Wang, X., Huang, W., Wei, S., Shang, Y., Gu, H., Wu, F., Lan, Z., Hu, M., Shi, H., & Wang, Y. (2020). Microplastics impair digestive performance but show little effects on antioxidant activity in mussels under low pH conditions. *Environmental Pollution*, 258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2019.113691>
- Wang, Y., Zhang, D., Zhang, M., Mu, J., Ding, G., Mao, Z., Cao, Y., Jin, F., Cong, Y., Wang, L., Zhang, W., & Wang, J. (2019). Effects of ingested polystyrene microplastics on brine shrimp, *Artemia parthenogenetica*. *Environmental Pollution*, 244, 715–722. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2018.10.024>
- Wang, Z., Fan, L., Wang, J., Xie, S., Zhang, C., Zhou, J., Zhang, L., Xu, G., & Zou, J. (2021). Insight into the immune and microbial response of the white-leg shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* to microplastics. *Marine Environmental Research*, 169(January), 105377. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2021.105377>
- Wesch, C., Bredimus, K., Paulus, M., & Klein, R. (2016). Towards the suitable monitoring of ingestion of

- microplastics by marine biota: A review. *Environmental Pollution*, 218, 1200–1208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2016.08.076>
- Wibowo, A. T., Nugrahapraja, H., Wahyuono, R. A., Islami, I., Haekal, M. H., Fardiansyah, Y., Sugiyo, P. W. W., Putro, Y. K., Fauzia, F. N., Santoso, H., Götz, F., Tangahu, B. V., & Luqman, A. (2021). Microplastic contamination in the human gastrointestinal tract and daily consumables associated with an Indonesian farming community. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(22). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132212840>
- Woo, C. K., & Bahna, S. L. (2011). Not all shellfish “allergy” is allergy! *Clinical and Translational Allergy*, 1(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2045-7022-1-3>
- Woods, M. N., Hong, T. J., Baughman, D., Andrews, G., Fields, D. M., & Matrai, P. A. (2020). Accumulation and effects of microplastic fibers in American lobster larvae (*Homarus americanus*). *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 157(February), 111280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2020.111280>
- World Fisheries and Aquaculture*. (2012).
- Wu, D., Feng, Y., Wang, R., Jiang, J., Guan, Q., Yang, X., Wei, H., Xia, Y., & Luo, Y. (2022). Pigment microparticles and microplastics found in human thrombi based on Raman spectral evidence. *Journal of Advanced Research*, xxx. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jare.2022.09.004>
- Wu, F., Wang, Y., Leung, J. Y. S., Huang, W., Zeng, J., Tang, Y., Chen, J., Shi, A., Yu, X., Xu, X., Zhang, H., & Cao, L. (2020). Accumulation of microplastics in typical commercial aquatic species: A case study at a productive aquaculture site in China. *Science of the Total Environment*, 708(36), 135432. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.135432>
- Wu, H., Hou, J., & Wang, X. (2023). A review of microplastic pollution in aquaculture: Sources, effects, removal strategies and prospects. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 252(August 2022), 114567. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2023.114567>
- Xiao, X., Liu, X., Mei, T., Xu, M., Lu, Z., Dai, H., Pi, F., & Wang, J. (2022). Estimation of contamination level in microplastic-exposed crayfish by laser confocal micro-Raman imaging. *Food Chemistry*, 397(June), 133844. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2022.133844>
- Xing, Y., Zhu, X., Duan, Y., Huang, J., Nan, Y., & Zhang, J. (2023). Toxic effects of nitrite and microplastics stress on histology, oxidative stress, and metabolic function in the gills of Pacific white shrimp, *Litopenaeus*

- vannamei. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 187(December 2022), 114531.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2022.114531>
- Yan, M., Li, W., Chen, X., He, Y., Zhang, X., & Gong, H. (2021). A preliminary study of the association between colonization of microorganism on microplastics and intestinal microbiota in shrimp under natural conditions. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 408(August 2020), 124882.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2020.124882>
- Yang, H., Sturmer, L. N., & Baker, S. (2016). Molluscan Shellfish Aquaculture and Production 1 Molluscan Shellfish Aquaculture in the United States. *UNIVERSITY OF FLORIDA, IFAS Extension*, 1–8.
- Yang, L., Cao, X., Cui, J., Wang, Y., Zhu, Z., Sun, H., Liang, W., Li, J., & Li, A. (2022). Holey Ti3C2 nanosheets based membranes for efficient separation and removal of microplastics from water. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 617, 673–682. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2022.03.055>
- Yang, W., & Li, Y. (2023). Association between Microorganisms and Microplastics : How Does It Change the Host – Pathogen Interaction and Subsequent Immune Response ?
- Yang, Z., Zhu, L., Liu, J., Cheng, Y., Waiho, K., Chen, A., & Wang, Y. (2022). Polystyrene microplastics increase Pb bioaccumulation and health damage in the Chinese mitten crab *Eriocheir sinensis*. *Science of the Total Environment*, 829, 154586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.154586>
- Yao, C., Liu, X., Wang, H., Sun, X., Qian, Q., & Zhou, J. (2021). Occurrence of Microplastics in Fish and Shrimp Feeds. *Bulletin of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, 107(4), 684–692.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00128-021-03328-y>
- Yao, L., Hui, L., Yang, Z., Chen, X., & Xiao, A. (2020). Freshwater microplastics pollution: Detecting and visualizing emerging trends based on Citespace II. *Chemosphere*, 245, 125627.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2019.125627>
- Yin, C. F., Xu, Y., & Zhou, N. Y. (2020). Biodegradation of polyethylene mulching films by a co-culture of *Acinetobacter* sp. strain NyZ450 and *Bacillus* sp. strain NyZ451 isolated from *Tenebrio molitor* larvae. *International Biodeterioration and Biodegradation*, 155(July), 105089.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibiod.2020.105089>
- Yusof, A., Sow, A. Y., Ramli, M. Z., Rak, E., & Wei, L. S. (2020). Growth performance of Asian clam *Corbicula*

- fluminea* (Müller, 1774) fed with different feeds in laboratory scale culture system. *Asian Fisheries Science*, 33(1), 50–57. <https://doi.org/10.33997/j.afs.2020.33.1.006>
- Zeng, Q., Yang, Q., Chai, Y., Wei, W., Luo, M., & Li, W. (2023). Polystyrene microplastics enhanced copper-induced acute immunotoxicity in red swamp crayfish (*Procambarus clarkii*). *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 249(October 2022), 114432. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2022.114432>
- Zhang, W., Tang, Y., Han, Y., Zhou, W., Shi, W., Teng, S., Ren, P., Xiao, G., Li, S., & Liu, G. (2022). Microplastics boost the accumulation of tetrabromobisphenol A in a commercial clam and elevate corresponding food safety risks. *Chemosphere*, 292(November 2021), 133499. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.133499>
- Zhang, X., Jin, Z., Shen, M., Chang, Z., Yu, G., Wang, L., & Xia, X. (2022). Accumulation of polyethylene microplastics induces oxidative stress, microbiome dysbiosis and immunoregulation in crayfish. *Fish and Shellfish Immunology*, 125(May), 276–284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fsi.2022.05.005>
- Zhang, X., Wang, X., & Yan, B. (2021). Single and combined effects of phenanthrene and polystyrene microplastics on oxidative stress of the clam (*Macraa veneriformis*). *Science of the Total Environment*, 771, 144728. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144728>
- Zhang, Y., Lu, J., Wu, J., Wang, J., & Luo, Y. (2020). Potential risks of microplastics combined with superbugs: Enrichment of antibiotic resistant bacteria on the surface of microplastics in mariculture system. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 187(September 2019), 109852. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2019.109852>
- Zheng, J., Qian, Y., & Zheng, X. (2023). Effects of stocking density on juvenile *Amphioctopus fangsiao* (Mollusca: Cephalopoda): Survival, growth, behavior, stress tolerance and biochemical response. *Aquaculture*, 567(January), 739243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2023.739243>
- Zhou, G. J., Ying, G. G., Liu, S., Zhou, L. J., Chen, Z. F., & Peng, F. Q. (2014). Simultaneous removal of inorganic and organic compounds in wastewater by freshwater green microalgae. *Environmental Sciences: Processes and Impacts*, 16(8), 2018–2027. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4em00094c>
- Zhou, J., Gui, H., Banfield, C. C., Wen, Y., Zang, H., Dippold, M. A., Charlton, A., & Jones, D. L. (2021). The microplastisphere: Biodegradable microplastics addition alters soil microbial community structure and

function. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 156(October 2020), 108211.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2021.108211>

Zhou, N., Wang, Z., Yang, L., Zhou, W., Qin, Z., & Zhang, H. (2023). Size-dependent toxicological effects of polystyrene microplastics in the shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* using a histomorphology, microbiome, and metabolic approach. *Environmental Pollution*, 316(P2), 120635.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2022.120635>

Zhu, J., Zhang, Q., Huang, Y., Jiang, Y., Li, J., Michal, J. J., Jiang, Z., Xu, Y., & Lan, W. (2021). Long-term trends of microplastics in seawater and farmed oysters in the Maowei Sea, China. *Environmental Pollution*, 273, 116450. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.116450>